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MODELING AND OPTIMIZING THE LOGISTIC ROUTING OF BIOMASS SIDE- FLOWS FOR CIRCULAR BIOECONOMY

Applying a Genetic Algorithm-Based Discrete
Event Simulation Approach

Faculty of Management and Business
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ABSTRACT

Kasper Eloranta: Modeling and Optimizing the Logistic Routing of Biomass Side-Flows for Circular Bioeconomy: Applying a Genetic Algorithm-Based Discrete Event Simulation Approach
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The acceleration of climate change has led regulators to impose constraints and incentives, encouraging both companies and individuals to align their actions with the goals of a green transition. There's a growing imperative to reduce waste and emissions while simultaneously maximizing the utilization of waste and by-products as valuable resources. These trends are driving societies toward adopting principles of the Circular Economy (CE). As the consumption of fossil energy sources needs to be reduced, the development and production of renewable energy sources become essential. Biogas, a form of renewable energy, offers an efficient way to utilize agricultural bio-based waste and side-flows, contributing to waste reduction and providing an alternative to fossil fuels. This approach aligns with the principles of the Circular Bioeconomy (CBE). However, establishing a circular supply chain for biogas production from biomasses is a complex endeavor. To ensure effective and sustainable operations within this system, logistics planning is crucial. This involves determining where, when, and how much biomass should be imported and transported for biogas production. It presents a multi-objective optimization problem, aiming to guarantee continuous biogas production while minimizing the costs associated with transporting biomass flows and other occurred inefficiencies.

This study models and simulates a circular supply chain that produces biogas from agricultural biowastes and side-flows. The supply chain in question encompasses a biogas plant, which is currently in the design phase but will later be constructed in the Kanta-Häme region of Finland. It also involves farms located in nearby areas, which are potential sources of biomass. The modeling aspect aims to optimize the logistics of collecting and transporting various types of biomasses from the farms to the biogas plant for use in the biogas production process. To achieve this optimization, a simulation model that utilizes a genetic algorithm (GA) has been developed. The objectives of the study include generating knowledge about both general and case-specific factors that should be considered when planning logistic routing to align with the principles of the Circular Bioeconomy (CBE). Another objective is to create an optimized routing plan for collecting resources for biogas production at the plant. Additionally, this study seeks to contribute to understanding of how time-critical factors, such as the quality of biomasses in terms of their energy potential, impact the optimization of logistic routing.

The study successfully maps the biomass potentials near the biogas plant and develops a methodology for optimizing the logistic routing of biomasses using the simulation model and the genetic algorithm. The study achieves the objective of generating an optimized routing proposal for the biogas plant in the case study, ensuring a continuous biogas production process. However, it is important to note that the results of the study may be suboptimal due to the complexity of the optimization problem and the time constraints of the research. The time-critical nature of biomasses should be considered when planning logistic systems for biogas production to avoid unnecessary costs. Limitations of the study include the use of non-farm-specific datasets, simplifying assumptions made in the simulation model, and time constraints that influenced the optimization stopping criteria and the potential for suboptimal results. Further research on this topic is necessary, either with more advanced methods or by allocating more computational time for optimization.

Keywords: Circular bioeconomy, logistic routing, optimization, biogas production, circular supply chain, simulation, genetic algorithm

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TIIVISTELMÄ

Kasper Eloranta: Biomassasivuvirtojen logistisen reitityksen mallinnus ja optimointi biokiertotalouden kontekstissa: geneettistä algoritmia käyttävän diskreetteihin tapahtumiin pohjautuvan simulaatiomenetelmän hyödyntäminen
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Ilmastonmuutoksen kiihtyminen on johtanut lainsäätäjät asettamaan rajoituksia ja kannustimia, jotka rohkaisevat yrityksiä ja yksilöitä mukauttamaan toimintaansa vihreän siirtymän tavoitteiden mukaisesti. Jatkuva kasvava tarve vähentää syntyviä jätteitä ja päästöjä samanaikaisesti jätteiden uudelleenkäytön ja hyödyntämisen maksimoiden vie yhteiskuntia kohti kiertotaloutta (engl. *circular economy*). Fossiilisten energialähteiden vähentämisen tarve synnyttää tarvetta kehittää ja tuottaa uudenlaisia uusiutuvan energian lähteitä. Biokaasu on tällainen uusiutuvan energian muoto, mikä mahdollistaa tehokkaan tavan maatalousjätteiden ja -sivutuotteiden hyödyntämiseen samalla vähentäen syntyvien jätteiden määrää ja tarjoten kestävä vaihtoehdon fossiilisille polttoaineille lähestyen biokiertotaloutta (engl. *circular bioeconomy*). Koska biokaasua tuottavat toimitusketjut ovat luonteeltaan monimutkaisia, niiden logistisia toimintoja on optimoitava jatkuvuuden turvaamiseksi. Suunnittelu kattaa päätökset siitä, mistä, milloin ja miten paljon eri tyyppisiä biomassoja tulisi noutaa ja kuljettaa biokaasulaitokselle kulutettavaksi biokaasun tuotannossa. Tällainen toimitusketjun logistiikka muodostaa monitavoitteellisen optimointiongelman, jonka tavoitteena on biokaasun tuotantoprosessin jatkuvuuden turvaaminen samalla minimoiden logistisen kuljetuksen sekä muiden mahdollisten tehottomuuksien aiheuttamat kustannukset.

Tässä tutkimuksessa mallinnetaan ja simuloidaan toimitusketjua, joka tuottaa biokaasua maataloudessa syntyvistä biojätteistä sekä sivuvirroista. Tarkasteltava toimitusketju sisältää suunnitelluvaiheessa olevan biokaasulaitoksen, joka tullaan sijoittamaan Kanta-Hämeen alueelle, sekä lähialueella biomassoja tuottavat tilat. Mallinnuksen tavoitteena on optimoida toimitusketjun logistinen reititys eri tyyppisten biomassojen keruun ja kuljetuksen suhteen. Optimoinnissa hyödynnetään geneettistä algoritmia simulaatiomallin kustannusfunktion minimoinnissa. Tutkimuksen tavoitteet kattavat ymmärryksen tuottamisen niistä yleisistä ja tapauskohtaisista tekijöistä, jotka on huomioitava toimitusketjun logistiikkaa optimoidessa varmistaakseen toimintojen yhteensopivuuden biokiertotalouden kanssa. Tavoitteena on myös tuottaa optimoitu reitityssuunnitelma kohdeyritykselle, joka vastaa biokaasulaitoksen suunnittelusta ja rakennuttamisesta. Reitityssuunnitelman tavoitteena on tuottaa kohdeyritykselle tietoa siitä, miten, mistä ja miten paljon eri biomassoja tulisi hakea. Lisäksi tutkimus tavoittelee ymmärryksen lisäämistä biomassojen sisältämien aikakriittisten tekijöiden vaikutuksesta logistisen reitityksen optimointiin.

Tutkimus onnistuu kartoittamaan laitoksen lähialueen biomassat sekä tuottamaan metodologian biomassojen logistisen reitityksen optimointiin osana biokaasun tuotantoa hyödyntämällä kehitettyä simulaatiomallia ja geneettistä algoritmia. Tutkimus saavuttaa tavoitteen optimoidun reitityksen tuottamisesta, mikä turvaa biokaasun tuotantoprosessin jatkuvuuden. Optimoitu reititys ei kuitenkaan välttämättä saavuta globaalia optimia. Biomassojen aikakriittinen luonne tulisi ottaa huomioon biokaasua tuottavien toimitusketjujen logistiikkaa suunniteltaessa välttääkseen ylimääräisiä kustannuksia. Tutkimuksen rajoitteisiin kuuluvat lähtödatan tilakohdattomuus, mallinnuksessa tehdyt välttämättömät yksinkertaistavat oletukset sekä tutkimusajan rajallisuus optimointiongelman monimutkaisuuteen nähden. Jatkotutkimusta aiheesta tarvitaan, joko käyttämällä edistyneempiä ja tehokkaampia menetelmiä tai allokoimalla tutkimukselle enemmän aikaa, jotta tulosten optimaalisuus voidaan varmistaa pidemmällä laskenta-ajalla.

Avainsanat: Biokiertotalous, logistinen reititys, optimointi, biokaasun tuotanto, kiertotalouden toimitusketju, simulointi, geneettinen algoritmi

Tämän julkaisun alkuperäisyys on tarkastettu Turnitin OriginalityCheck –ohjelmalla.

PREFACE

These last five years studying at Tampere University have been an incredible learning journey for me. I have developed my skills in solving surprisingly complicated problems by trusting my rational and logical thought process, which has developed to an extent of which I am proud. More importantly, I have evolved as a person, friend, and companion. Every single person who has had even the slightest impact on my journey deserves acknowledgment of my appreciation and thankfulness.

The study I am happily wrapping up today, at some level, summarizes the key driving interests that motivate me to pursue greatness. It includes elements representing the fundamental drive for me to navigate the complicated world through logic and numerical analysis, which was one of the main reasons I applied for and studied the first year of my studies in a program of technical physics and mathematics. During that first year, I realized I wanted to utilize my skills and interests in a field that enables me to provide more practical impacts and benefits to the companies or organizations I work for or with. That is why I decided to apply to the program of Industrial Engineering and Management, and now, four and a half years later, I am writing the preface of my master's thesis, after which I will graduate from that program. My enthusiasm for data science and the utilization of advanced computational methods to provide real-world business value is also evident within this study. If I am lucky, someday I might get to work with these topics I feel passionate about. We shall wait and see what the future holds for me.

I want to thank my supervisors at HAMK Smart, Olli Koskela and Iivari Kunttu, for providing me with this opportunity to conduct my study within an interesting project. Supervisors from Tampere University, Ulla Saari and Juho Kanninen, also deserve great thanks for providing guiding principles and significant assistance to me in the process of writing this thesis.

I am grateful for the friends I have made and have managed to stay in contact with during these busy years of studying. Thanks for providing opportunities to relax from studies for the most interesting ways of spending time. Stay just the way you are, as awesome.

Lastly, I want to thank my beloved fiancée, Eeva, for supporting me and always counting on me during these years. Your unceasing support for my ambitious endeavors is admirable. May we continue this tremendous and exciting journey of ours with the excitement and trust for the future.

In Tampere, Finland, 20.9.2023

Kasper Eloranta

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ABBREVIATIONS AND NOTATIONS

AD	Anaerobic Digestion
BCP	Biomass Collection Problem
BRBPP	Biomass Routing and Biogas Production Problem
CE	Circular Economy
CBE	Circular Bioeconomy
CBM	Circular Business Model
CSR	Corporate Social Responsibility
EOQ	Economic Order Quantity
EPQ	Economic Production Quantity
GA	Genetic Algorithm
GHG	Greenhouse Gases
HAMK	Häme University of Applied Sciences
HRT	Hydraulic Retention Time
LuKe	Natural Resources Institute Finland
OLR	Organic Loading Rate
RL	Reinforcement Learning
TS	Total Solids
TSP	Travelling Salesman Problem
VRP	Vehicle Routing Problem
VRPTW	Vehicle Routing Problem with Time Windows
$\Delta m_{t,i}$	an accumulation of biomass at the day t on the pickup site i
m_t	a daily expected accumulation of biomass at the site i
M_i	the annual accumulation of grass or straw at site i
ε_i	randomized vector determining the days of biomass jumps at pickup sites producing grass and straw
$r_{l,d}$	biomass weekly volume loss coefficient due passive drying

$V_{b,w}$	the volume of biomass b after w weeks of drying
$r_{m,d}$	biomass weekly moisture decrease coefficient due passive drying
$M_{b,w}$	the level of moisture of biomass b after w weeks of drying
$\Delta t_{i,l}$	the pickup duration for the pickup site i with a load level of l
T	setting time for pickup operation
v_m	collection rate of biomass m
S_p	size of the population utilized within GA's optimization
N_g	number of genes within a solution proposal
TC	total costs of the system caused during a simulation period
c_{ovld}	the cost of one day of overload at a pickup site
$OVLD_i$	the number of overloading days at pickup site i
$C_{vehicles}$	costs caused by vehicles during a simulation period
p_f	the price of fuel
c_f	the assumed fuel consumption of vehicles
ODO_i	the total mileage driven by vehicle i
n	the number of vehicles
c_{ovth}	the assumed cost of overtime work
OVT_i	the total overtime work of vehicle i
c_{wv}	unit cost for a vehicle visiting wrong type of pickup site
WV_i	the number of wrong visits carried out by vehicle i
C_{bgp}	costs caused by emerged inefficiencies within the biogas production
c_{pdst}	assumed unit cost of production stoppage due biomass shortage
PDST	the number of production stoppages occurred during the simulation
c_{ovf}	the cost of one day of overfilling biogas plant's storage
OVF	the number of days of overfilled storage within the biogas plant
c_{exim}	the cost of biomass import after annual demand is satisfied
EXIM	the number of unnecessary imports occurred within the simulation

c_{dw} cost for one ton of dilution water consumed within biogas production

DW the total consumption of dilution water during the simulation in tons

1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter introduces the topic of the study by defining the context of it and motivating its importance. Later in the chapter, the research problem, research questions, scope, and objectives of the study are defined and presented. The chapter closes by summarizing the structure of the study.

1.1 Research background

Mankind is facing one of its greatest challenges with the inevitable fact of climate change and its progression. Due to regulators' acknowledgment of climate change, many objectives and guidelines have been set to ensure the compatibility of individuals' and companies' actions with the green transition. States and non-profit organizations play a crucial role here since it is often their decision what kind of magiyaentures they are funding. In Europe, the European Union (EU) is one of the major operators accelerating the green transition, having set a goal to become climate neutral by 2050 (Bauer et al. 2021). EU's Green Deal policies, with planned investment of a total of €1 trillion, are seeking ways to speed up the green transition in different industries by researching the topics of sustainable energy production, carbon-neutral fuels and enabling the usage of more circular products and resources in energy-intensive industries with less or zero waste and pollution. (Bauer et al. 2021)

An urgent need to reduce consumption and mitigate emissions has led academics and companies operating in different fields to seek ways to reinvent prevailing business models and supply chains to become more sustainable. Increasing sustainability may sometimes require necessary trade-offs with maximizing profitability and operational performance (Varenova et al. 2013). A current and predominant perspective to this issue in which one is seeking ways to improve the sustainability of operations by increasing re-usage and recycling of materials, enhancing cost-effectiveness, and mitigating emissions without compromising profitability or performance, is denoted by the term circular economy (CE). The advantages of the CE have been studied and argued widely – it has been found that a total shift to a circular economy would reduce greenhouse-gas emissions by up to 70 %, simultaneously growing the workforce by about 4 % in seven European nations. (Stahel, 2016)

The principle of the CE provides interesting opportunities to replace non-renewable energy sources by utilizing waste management as a part of energy production. Especially

managing and properly processing the biomass side-flows offer considerable opportunities to produce green energy (Bellezoni et al. 2022). Waste-to-energy systems, in general, offer opportunities to improve the operational efficiency and cost-effectiveness of actors producing waste and capable of generating energy out of it instead of using raw materials in the first place. Proper procession of biomass side-flows enables industries to use their waste to produce energy for their needs, which is greatly consistent with circular economy principles. (Monteiro & Ferreira, 2022) However, bioenergy production may have an increasing impact on the ecological footprint (Wang et al. 2020). That raises more questions on how bioenergy production and its resource flows should be organized and optimized to utilize the maximum amount of wastes and side-flows, without compromising emissions and ecological footprint.

Enhancing the optimization of resource flows and logistical operations stands as a significant means toward attaining the principles of circularity. Depending on the type of resource, transportation time may become a critical factor due to the pollution of resources. For instance, this is the case for the animal manure transported to be used as a fertilizer for plants (Kamilaris & Prenafeta-Boldú, 2021). Efficient transportation of manure would, therefore, mitigate resource pollution, improve the valorization rate of manure as a resource rather than waste, and align with the principles of the circular economy. However, transportation itself comes with environmental and economic costs, which should also be taken into consideration in optimization. (Kamilaris & Prenafeta-Boldú, 2021) While optimizing the supply chain configurations, the offering and demand of actors and the balance between them must also be considered (Balaman et al. 2018). Due to the complicated nature of circular supply chains, digital and analytical tools become a necessity in modeling and optimizing those networks.

Sufficient digital capabilities and technologies are critical factors in enabling circular business models. It has been argued widely that digital technologies provide opportunities to improve resource flows and value creation and capture and enable innovations for circular business models to emerge. (Ranta et al. 2021) It is important to note that digital technologies contribute to the circular economy in two fundamentally different ways. They provide knowledge creation and sharing, enabling decision-makers to rationalize factors affecting decisions to optimize resource flows and value creation in a way that is aligned with the principles of CE (Ranta et al. 2021). They also provide analytical tools to be used as assistance in decision-making, such as modeling and optimizing waste-to-energy supply chains with multi-objective decision-making algorithms (Balaman et al. 2018). Through these kinds of use cases, digital technologies catalyze many kinds of business model and process innovations (Ranta et al. 2021) that enable aligning the

operations with the principles of CE across industries. By embracing practices and principles of CE and applying them with advanced computational and digital methods, mankind may achieve carbon neutrality and better tomorrow via a green transition to living to fight another day.

1.2 Scope and objectives of the research

This study is conducted as a part of the EU-funded research venture BioKanta. The venture studies and seeks sustainable ways to maximize bioenergy production, improve current practices of it, and enhance the circular use of waste and side-flows generated by agriculture, the manufacturing industry, and waste and water management facilities (Kymäläinen & Tampio, 2023). The venture focuses on improving circularity and bioenergy production in the region of Kanta-Häme in Finland. BioKanta is implemented in collaboration among the research units Bio and Smart at Häme University of Applied Sciences (HAMK) and with the Natural Resources Institute Finland (LuKe). (Kymäläinen & Tampio, 2023)

This study is part of the first phase of the BioKanta. In the first phase of the venture, the objective is to identify and bring into use the potential of bioenergy production and recycling in resource flows in Kanta-Häme (Tampio, 2023). This includes notifying and connecting the actors operating the bioenergy facilities with the local actors producing potential waste and resource side-flows to be used in bioenergy production and enabling collaboration among them. The first phase also includes planning and optimizing the logistic operations amongst the notified actors and with the upcoming large biogas plant under construction. (Tampio, 2023) This study focuses on one large, centralized biogas plant under construction and optimizing the logistic routing of the resource flows that enable the operation of the upcoming biogas plant. The research focus of the study is illustrated in Figure 1, which represents the intersection of the objectives of the first phase of BioKanta.

Figure 1. The research focus of the study.

In more detail, this study focuses on modeling and optimizing the logistic routing of biomass side-flows that will be utilized by the centralized biogas plant as part of its bioenergy production process. These biomass side-flows consist of manures, grasses, and straws. Spatial data mapping of biomass potentials located nearby the biogas plant is also conducted as a prerequisite for modeling and optimizing the biomass side-flows.

Objectives of the study include generating knowledge about and understanding the general and case-specific circular bioeconomy goals, practices and prevailing dynamics that are required to consider in modeling the routing of flows, enabling better the utilization of circular business models. Understanding the circularity goals and the possibilities and constraints of its practices play a critical role if one is seeking to model and simulate a complicated logistic network with multiple factors and conditions to consider.

The study also aims to produce knowledge of how the routing of biomass side-flows should be organized by the case company which can be used as assistance in the case company's decision-making processes. Along with this, as an additional objective, the study aims to generate knowledge about comparing the results of optimized routing under two different simulation schemes, with one assuming the quality of biomasses in terms of their energy potential is not dependent on time-critical factors, and the other assuming time-critical factors exist. This comparison could have a practical impact on optimizing the routing of biomass side-flows under circularity principles, especially if the simulation results vary significantly due to the assumption of time-critical factors.

1.3 Research problem and questions

The research problem may be formatted accordingly with the following three research questions this study seeks answers for. The first one aims to understand the practices, opportunities, and constraints of circular bioeconomy in the context of optimizing logistic operations, with a general and case-specific perspective and is formatted accordingly:

RQ1: What are the key factors to consider in modeling and optimizing biomass side-flow routing to ensure logistic operations compatibility with circular bioeconomy practices?

The second objective leverages the information obtained from addressing the first research question and aims to establish a consensus on how the case company should organize logistic routing within the context of its prevailing conditions, constraints, and practices, as identified by the response to the first question. The second research question is as follows:

RQ2: How should the routing of biomass side-flows be organized to align the logistic operations with circular bioeconomy practices and dynamically optimize the routing of biomass side-flows based on selected criteria?

The third research question seeks to find new ways to enhance the optimization of logistics by creating new knowledge of the prevailing dynamics affecting the optimal solution. This is done by comparing the optimized solutions of logistic routing, simulated with currently approved circumstances, and expanding these circumstances by including new factors to the optimization procedure that has been neglected before.

RQ3: How does the consideration of decreasing biomass quality over time affect the optimal routing solution compared to the optimized result?

1.4 Structure of the study

This study is in six chapters. The first one introduces the background of the study, sets scope and objectives of it, and defines the research problem and questions. The second chapter presents the literature review, discussing the concepts of circular bioeconomy, circular business models, and biomass utilization through biogas production. It also illustrates the case company's supply chain and analyzes related circular business models, success, and risk factors, with a focus on logistic optimization. The literature review concludes by presenting a theoretical framework of factors, constraints, and possibilities to consider for the methodology of logistic routing optimization of biomass side-flows, serving as an answer for the first research question.

The third chapter presents the research methodology for this study, including a conceptual description of the optimization problem of biomass routing and biogas production, data collection, description, processing, and model development. It covers topics such as processing and visualizing data in Python (Magiya, 2019), utilizing the KMeans clustering algorithm (Jeffares, 2019), the SimPy library for discrete-event simulation (Team SimPy, 2020), and the genetic algorithm used in optimization (Gracia et al. 2014; Katoch et al. 2021; Niemitalo & Ekkerman, 2022). The chapter concludes by assessing the validity and reliability of the methodology.

The results, answering the second and third research questions, are presented in the fourth chapter. This presentation includes the optimization trajectories of the optimized routings and their performance in both cases. Furthermore, the results are validated by benchmarking them against randomized and baseline routing. In the fifth chapter, the results are discussed, analyzed, and compared, leading to the presentation of the study's key findings. Finally, the sixth chapter concludes the study by addressing its theoretical and practical implications, assessing the quality and limitations of the study, and suggesting ideas for future research on the topic.

2 CIRCULAR BIOECONOMY

This chapter reviews the literature regarding the circular bioeconomy. Firstly, the concepts of bioeconomy, circular economy (CE), and circular bioeconomy (CBE) are defined and distinguished. Secondly, the conceptual frameworks for CE and CBE are presented, discussed, and compared. In the third, fourth, and fifth sections of the chapter, the perspective of the literature review is taken to a more practical level by discussing and analyzing the implementation of circular business models (CBM) aligned with the principles of the circular bioeconomy in the context of the study's case company, its supply chain, and the related success and risk factors. The chapter closes by synthesizing the literature review.

2.1 From bioeconomy and circular economy to circular bioeconomy

The term bioeconomy refers to parts of the society and economy that utilize renewable biological resources from land and sea to produce materials, food, and energy. These parts of the society and the economy cover the sectors and associated services that process, produce or are in contact with any part of the supply chain involving biological resources. (Giampietro, 2019) One example of the bioeconomy is the utilization of agricultural waste and side-flows, such as manure and straw, as a resource in biogas production, in cooperation with actors from the energy and agriculture industries and their stakeholders. The term is intended to remind people of the biological origin of the economic process and highlight the problem of limited usable and accessible resources that are unevenly located and unequally appropriated (Giampietro, 2019). However, due to the renewable nature of bio-resources, they can be said to be naturally circular at some level (Salvador et al. 2021). The natural circularity of bio-resources may already enable greater environmental sustainability compared to practices using fossil resources (Paredes-Sánchez et al. 2019).

Since the diversity of bioeconomies is greatly dependent on local characteristics and the possible scarcity of required resources, cooperation among the actors in the bioeconomy should be developed to enable more efficient utilization of circularity via the renewable nature of bio-resources. With more circular usage of bio-resources, economic growth and environmental benefits may be achieved by maximizing the value of resources and minimizing the consumption of virgin or non-renewable resources, approaching the principles of the CE (Salvador et al. 2021).

The CE has gained an increasing amount of attention and popularity during the last few years. This has led to a multitude of partly congruent and vague definitions of the CE by the science community (Korhonen et al. 2018; Prieto-Sandoval et al. 2018). Differing definitions of the CE have generated a need to define a general framework for it. It is important to understand the differences between the CE and sustainable development, whereas the principles of CE offer tools to attain sustainable development. Understanding the prevailing dynamics affecting circularity which are dependent on the level of perspective also plays a crucial role if sustainability is sought via circularity. Economic, environmental, and social dimensions of sustainability should also be considered to adjust the CE practices in a way that serves the purpose of reaching the selected type of sustainability. (Korhonen et al. 2018; Prieto-Sandoval et al. 2018)

Stahel (2016), Korhonen et al. (2018) and Kirchherr et al. (2018) discuss the defining factors of the CE, its opportunities, and its restrictions. The main aim of the CE is to close loops in industrial ecosystems. This is achieved by repurposing goods near the end of their useful life, thus reducing waste. This approach profoundly shifts the economic paradigm from production to sufficiency. The focus is on deriving value from existing goods and manufacturing only when necessary. This fundamental departure from non-circular economies classifies CE business models into two non-exclusive groups. The first prioritizes reuse and prolonging product life through repairs and upgrades. The second group seeks value by transforming goods and materials into valuable resources through recycling. (Stahel, 2016) However, implementing circular practices and business models must address challenges arising from current industry practices to achieve sustainable development. (Korhonen et al. 2018; Kirchherr et al. 2018).

The challenges of implementing CE practices arise from the physical scale of the economy and its impact on sustainability, as well as the path-dependency and lock-in effects (Korhonen et al. 2018; Kirchherr et al. 2018). Even if CE practices increase the economy's scale, harmful impacts can result (Korhonen et al. 2018). Jevons' paradox, described as lower costs leading to increased production and consumption, complicates matters (Alcott, 2005; Korhonen et al. 2018). Economic growth presents the "boomerang effect", where pollution-intensive industries may relocate to poorer countries during sustainability efforts (Korhonen et al. 2018).

Path-dependencies and lock-in challenges stem from market dynamics. Early solutions dominate, hindering new CE innovations. (Korhonen et al. 2018) Pricing dynamics of recycled materials are perceived to be more volatile in comparison with prices of virgin materials, influencing the consumption behavior of the markets (Grafström & Aasma,

2021). Kirchherr et al.'s (2018) study highlights barriers to CE: cultural (consumer disinterest, linear operations), market (low virgin material prices, high upfront costs), regulatory (policy framework gaps), and technological (lack of circular design and remanufacturing) barriers. Technological deficiency can be further extended to encompass a lack of technological capabilities. Businesses without suitable IT systems might find it difficult to evaluate costs and profits associated with circularity investments using their operational data (Grafström & Aasma, 2021). This can lead to unsupported decisions to either reject or accept investments in CE. While businesses prioritize cost and competition, policymakers recognize the importance of regulatory shifts toward supportive CE frameworks (Kirchherr et al. 2018).

Circularity brings some additional benefits if its requirements are satisfied. Applying circular practices, such as recycling and reprocessing of materials, generates jobs and saves energy with lower resource consumption and waste (Stahel, 2016). By considering these kinds of indirect benefits of the CE, challenges for implementing CE practices profitably that are hard to affect directly, such as thermodynamic and system boundary limits (Korhonen et al. 2018), may be addressed indirectly. For instance, a car owner choosing between buying new tires or repairing old ones illustrates the circular ecosystem. Waste management services are crucial for this system to work, allowing used items to be resold rather than discarded. The main goal is profitable waste management to enhance circularity, achieved by minimizing collection and disposal costs. To optimize resource value over time, proper markets and collection points are needed for recycling, based on the material being considered. (Stahel, 2016)

While defining the marketplaces and collection points that enable circularity, the cost caused by using the circular channel of recycling materials to individuals must be considered. For instance, one may not sort the waste he produces, if dumping all goods into mixed waste containers is perceived significantly more cost-efficient to the individual than sorting the waste. However, if sorting of waste is sufficiently encouraged through selected incentives and restrictions, the collection of certain types of waste, especially bio-based waste, becomes possible. This enables the implementation of a circular bioeconomy and its opportunities.

The circular bioeconomy (CBE) refers to the overlapping parts of the bioeconomy and the CE. One definition of the CBE states that its implementation enables sustainable economic growth in developed countries by considering the CE as what should be done, and the bioeconomy as how it should be done (Giampietro, 2019). The implementation of CBE promotes more sustainable manufacturing practices in general, leading to the transformation towards a broader usage of renewable bioresources, which are converted

into bioenergy and other bio-based products. This, in turn, generates new jobs and industries (European Commission, n.d., as cited in Giampietro, 2019).

The CBE is a system that maximizes the utilization of bioresources in manufacturing and energy production, adds high sustainable value with the reuse and cascaded use of materials, and minimizes the virgin resource input from the natural environment, as well as the emissions and resource outputs to the environment. In comparison to the bioeconomy, the CBE aims to keep bioresources within the technical cycle for as long as possible. (Salvador et al. 2021) Therefore, the CBE aims to maximize the total value generated per unit of a resource rather than maximizing the value generated per resource unit in a fixed measure of time or usage. The approach of solely seeking the best and most effective economic impact in a fixed service life of a resource is an old-fashioned and less innovative approach, typically implemented in the context of the bioeconomy, not in the context of CBE (Salvador et al. 2021).

2.2 Conceptual framework for circular bioeconomy

Prieto-Sandoval et al. (2018) propose a framework for the CE, highlighting its relationship with eco-innovation. In this section, the conceptual framework of CE is reviewed and the CBE's positioning in it is examined. After that, the conceptual framework of CBE presented by Wei et al. (2022) is analyzed in detail and discussed and compared to the CE framework by discussing the similarities between the frameworks.

Analysis of Prieto-Sandoval et al. (2018) suggests that the CE should include four main components: minimizing resource demand, a multi-level approach, importance for sustainable development, and the connection between the CE and innovation (Prieto-Sandoval et al. 2018). The first and third components align with Stahel's (2016) definition, emphasizing the minimization of resource consumption and the enablement of sustainable development. The multi-level approach and connection to eco-innovation offer new insights into understanding the CE.

Yuan et al.'s (2006) research informed Prieto-Sandoval et al.'s (2018) introduction of three levels of the CE implementation: micro-, meso-, and macro-level. At the micro-level, companies focus on implementing CE practices that serve their own interests, such as reducing costs and enhancing their reputation (Prieto-Sandoval et al. 2018). While this may generate economic benefits, it is important for regulators to incentivize companies to operate with circular principles to ensure that CE practices are implemented for the right reasons.

At the meso-level of the CE, companies participate in industrial symbiosis, which benefits both the regional economy and the environment (Prieto-Sandoval et al. 2018). The focus is on encouraging the creating of eco-industrial parks and networks generating both types of benefits (Geng et al. 2012; Prieto-Sandoval et al. 2018). An example of a meso-level network is a group of companies operating in different industries, whose operations are related in some way. Cooperation between these companies creates economic and environmental benefits, such as a biogas network producing and selling renewable energy. This reduces the need for non-renewable energy sources and provides a sustainable alternative.

The macro-level of the CE involves focusing on cities, municipalities, provinces, and states, and their circularity. This includes developing eco-cities, eco-municipalities, and eco-provinces, which require institutions to raise awareness and set boundaries and incentives to implement the CE practices. (Yuan et al. 2006; Prieto-Sandoval et al. 2018) Raising awareness for the need to improve circularity affects the funding of research, leading to more sustainable development. This research provides opportunities for eco-innovation, which is crucial for improving the CE practices and achieving sustainable development.

Eco-innovations drive the improvement of existing practices across all three levels of the CE (Prieto-Sandoval et al. 2018). They are defined as improved products, services, processes, marketing changes, or organizational changes that decrease waste and emissions across the entire supply chain of the given context and reduce the use of natural/virgin resources (Hojnik & Ruzzier, 2016). Ultimately, eco-innovations address the environmental impact of innovation by promoting more efficient resource usage while simultaneously minimizing the harmful environmental impacts of current practices (Hojnik & Ruzzier, 2016).

Three determinants of eco-innovations in the CE are identified: policy and regulation, supply side, and demand side. Policy and regulation determine the legal framework for the CE that should support circular supply side actions such as cleaner production. (Prieto-Sandoval et al. 2018) Incentives are also provided to execute sustainable action to gain additional benefits. Demand side determinants consist mainly of consumers, who should be able to acquire sustainable behavior and accept eco-innovative products in the market instead of less sustainable products (Prieto-Sandoval et al. 2018). Policy and regulation determinants may influence demand-side determinants through market dynamics, such as sales restrictions or taxes on non-sustainable products. Hidden determinants such as market-specific factors can also affect the capability of actors to adopt

sustainable behavior, such as the government's view on the importance of green transition. Acceptance of the importance of green transition can lead to funding research on the CE, enabling more eco-innovations to emerge.

In more detail, eco-innovations may be divided into product, process, and organizational eco-innovations, which emerge from environmental R&D investments driven by factors such as regulatory requirements, investments, market pull, operational efficiency needs, and cost savings (Hojnik & Ruzzier, 2016). As a result, eco-innovations may not be solely technological; they can also encompass organizational, social, or institutional innovations. This is why they can emerge from either companies or nonprofit organizations, and they may not always be tradable in the markets. Due to the complex and multifaceted nature of eco-innovations, an interdisciplinary approach is usually required for their emergence. An interdisciplinary approach is necessary to understand the economic market factors that determine the success of innovation. On the other hand, the innovation itself must be sufficiently advanced to generate enough environmental value, such as waste reduction and minimized use of virgin materials. (Hojnik & Ruzzier, 2016)

Since it is argued that the CE offers tools to achieve sustainability (Korhonen et al. 2018; Prieto-Sandoval et al. 2018), a similar argument can be made for the necessity of eco-innovations to emerge to design and enhance the current CE practices. These practices enable more sustainable operations and, ultimately, sustainable development by consistently improving the adopted methods through eco-innovation. Sustainability is defined as the attainment of a well-coordinated balance among economic, social, and environmental performance across different generations (Geissdoerfer et al. 2017). This equilibrium involves respecting nature's capacity for self-regeneration by avoiding overconsumption and staying within the limits of nature's production capacity. The three pillars of sustainability – people, profit, and planet – encapsulate the idea of a necessary balance among environmental, economic, and social dimensions while striving for sustainability. These pillars aim to preserve the functions of the Earth's ecosystems, nurturing well-being, health, and security, all of which are crucial for ensuring a sustainable future. (Geissdoerfer et al. 2017)

However, since sustainability may be perceived as a high-level concept, its set of goals, which involves pursuing simultaneous benefits for the environment, economy, and society (Geissdoerfer et al. 2017), is broader and less defined than the corresponding set of goals for the CE. On the other hand, the goals of CE are centered around closing the loops within material flow systems (Geissdoerfer et al. 2017). If the CE practices are considered as prerequisites for sustainability and similarly regard eco-innovations as prerequisites for the CE practices, it becomes essential to consider the factors that drive

and influence the adoption of eco-innovations (Bossle et al. 2016; Hojnik & Ruzzier 2016). These forces driving the success of eco-innovations may ultimately determine whether sustainable development is achieved or not.

The widespread adoption of eco-innovation requires innovation itself to emerge and circumstances to adjust for broad adoption across actors in the examined market or industry. This entails considering established factors that impact eco-innovation adoption at the company level (Bossle et al. 2016; Hojnik & Ruzzier 2016). Eco-innovation's emergence is primarily driven by regulations and market pull factors, which are crucial for its emergence within companies (Hojnik & Ruzzier, 2016). These factors, aside from the type of eco-innovation, play a vital role in its development, adoption, and diffusion phases (Hojnik & Ruzzier, 2016).

Factors influencing the adoption of eco-innovations and achieving sustainable development can be categorized as internal and external factors within an organization (Bossle et al. 2016). Regulatory and market demands also impact eco-innovation adoption, compelling organizations to embrace new practices, resources, or processes. For instance, customers and stakeholders may demand operations that align with corporate social responsibility (CSR), which can be enhanced by impactful eco-innovations. Internal factors affecting eco-innovation adoption at the company level encompass environmental capabilities, strategy, human resources, and the drive for operational efficiency. Industry sector and company size similarly influence the adoption process. (Bossle et al. 2016)

Based on the previously presented review and analysis on the CE, an illustration of its central concepts is presented on the Figure 2. The illustration includes the main process of the CE representing the ideas of circular material flows and the crucial role of innovation in enabling the implementation and development of the CE practices. Subsequent and key social, environmental, and economic benefits are also illustrated and emphasized. See page 14 for the Figure 2. The positioning of the CBE in the context of the CE will be discussed next.

Figure 2. Conceptual model for the circular economy (CE). Graph adapted from Stahel (2016) and Korhonen et al. (2018).

Since the CBE is a sub-concept of the CE that focuses on biological materials (Giampietro, 2019), it can be argued that the framework presented in Figure 2 for the CE is still applicable when discussing the CBE. However, one must consider the potential boundary conditions established by the CBE. For example, the variety of extracted resources significantly decreases when focusing on the CBE rather than the CE. A common mechanism used in the CE manufacturing industries to repair goods simply disappears in the CBE. While inspected materials have processing value in the terms of energy and nutrients, there are no logical ways to repair or refurbish them, limiting the ways in which the materials can be used compared to the CE. Additional examples could be easily generated to highlight the differences between the CBE and the CE. Nevertheless, in the context of Figure 2, especially its inner circle that represents the material flow in a circular system, the group of alternative ways to execute operations in each phase (use, innovation, extracted resources, manufacturing, distribution, and use) is significantly narrowed when the focus shifts from the CE to the CBE. Thus, one should consider the CBE-special boundary conditions and restrictions caused by the focus of biological materials.

The CBE is argued to bring environmental and economic benefits by Mohan et al. (2018) and Salvador et al. (2021). The benefits are achieved via the recovery of bio-based wastes and byproducts, preventing pollution, and promoting valorization, allowing the sale of wastes as marketable products with added value, thus enabling economic growth (Salvador et al. 2021). It can also be argued that the CBE brings social benefits, but not as much as the CE in general. The CBE's contribution to generating jobs and industries in capturing the value of bioresources is undisputed, whereas the complete supply chain of biomass procession generates a variety of jobs in capturing the value. However, the other typical aspects of the CE's social benefits may not be as predominant in the context of the CBE. The sense of community, cooperation, and sharing functions and services are probably less relevant in the CBE since the boundary conditions of the CBE do not naturally encourage the sharing economy as strongly as the CE in general. Reuse, refurbishment, and other measures that encourage the sharing of recycled goods are generally more applicable in the CE.

Figure 3. Conceptual model for the circular bioeconomy (CBE). Graph adapted from Wei et al. (2022).

The conceptual model for the CBE presented by Wei et al. (2022) encapsulates the positioning of the CBE in the broader context of the CE, in comparison with the presentation of Figure 2 which is based on the CE frameworks presented by Stahel (2016), Prieto-Sandoval et al. (2018), and Korhonen et al. (2018). In the CBE, inputs of circular system consist of bio-based-resources used as substitutes of non-renewable sources, whose utilization enhance efficiency and effectiveness of production and services along the supply chain of biomass utilization, ending up with reduced greenhouse gases (GHG) and emissions and improved sustainability (Wei et al. 2022). Biotechnology innovation, market needs of bio-products and services and the incentive and constrain structures set by the policy framework together guides and accelerates the development of circular bioeconomy and its direction (Wei et al. 2022). This conceptual model for the CBE is illustrated above in the Figure 3.

2.3 Circular business models for valorizing agricultural bio-waste and side-flows in biogas production

To adopt the practices of the CBE, businesses operating in related fields must align their operations with the principles of the CBE and circular business models (CBM). In general, a business model is a conceptual representation of how and what value the com-

pany aims to deliver to its customers (Salvador et al. 2021). Salvador et al. (2021) analyzed key aspects of business models for the CBE. These aspects include technological innovations, customer segments and relationships, value creation process, logistics and biomass collection, biowaste and by-product valorization, cost structure, resilient value chains, and strategic partnerships. The implementation of a business model for the CBE enables the production, utilization, and management of bioresources with high added value. This approach reduces material leakage and optimizes resource flows through cascading and upcycling. (Salvador et al. 2021) The role of optimizing logistics and biomass material collection should be emphasized here, as it is a cost that can be greatly affected. Thus, if collection points are chosen wisely and the logistic operations for collecting and transporting them are cost-effective, the total value created by the CBE system may be maximized, ensuring the alignment of implemented practices with the principles of the CBE.

Circular systems that valorize biowaste and biomass side-flows simultaneously utilize several CBMs. Based on the typology for CBMs that valorize agro-waste proposed by Donner et al. (2020), it can be argued that within the system comprising farms, logistic operators, biogas facilities, and bioenergy users, the CBMs of a biogas plant, agropark, and support structure (Donner et al. 2020) are applied in the given context. The simultaneous utilization of multiple CBMs also highlights the importance of cooperating with research organizations and raising awareness within relevant stakeholders by establishing strong strategic partnerships within farms, carriers, biogas facilities, and end customers to ensure the compatibility and synergies between the CBMs, as noted by Donner et al. (2020) and Salvador et al. (2021) as well. The presence of multiple actors in the circular supply chain and the overlapping of multiple CBMs result in a potential uneven distribution of costs and benefits in valorizing agro-waste and side-flows, as noted by Donner et al. (2020). Hence, the importance of strategic partnerships is emphasized again to ensure a sufficient transparency in the circular supply chain, satisfying the needs and requirements of all related actors. This enables continuity in their businesses and, ultimately, aligns the implemented practices with the principles of CBE through cooperation within the circular network.

2.3.1 Anaerobic digestion

As mentioned earlier, circular systems valorizing biomasses utilize multiple CBMs simultaneously, which also applies to the supply chain of the case company in this study. In short, biomasses consisting of agricultural waste and side-flows, such as manures and

straws, are generated on farms as part of their daily operations. These biomasses contain energy potential if effectively valorized (Donner et al. 2020). The main principle for valorizing these biomasses is anaerobic digestion (AD) (Monlau et al. 2015; Donner et al. 2020). AD is a biological process in which the degradable fraction of organic matrix is converted into biogas and/or biofuel, which can be used to produce heat and energy (Monlau et al. 2015). However, the implementation of AD requires significant technological investments, which are typically greater than what farmers are willing to afford (Donner et al. 2020). This is why large, centralized biogas plants, such as the plant being constructed by the case company, are necessary. These plants make substantial investments in the technology required for the valorization process and collect the required biomasses from multiple farms. However, collecting the biomasses from multiple pickup-sites brings the problem of planning the logistic operations from the farms to the facility. As noted by Salvador et al. (2021), the cost-effective logistic operations are crucial for CBMs to succeed. By noting that the prices of bioenergy are usually fixed by national policies (Donner et al. 2020), the importance of cost-effective logistics is justified once again. It is a key factor in the cost structure of the supply chain, greatly affecting the total net value generated.

Depending on the chosen AD processing technology, certain thresholds for the composition of input flows are established. AD processing technologies can be broadly categorized into two types: dry and wet processes (Hadin & Eriksson, 2016). The differentiating factor between dry and wet processes is the total solids (TS) content in the material to be digested. If the TS rate of the process is below 15%, it is considered a wet process; otherwise, it is a dry process. (Hadin & Eriksson, 2016)

The biogas reactor of the case company is designed for wet processes, aiming for a 15% TS rate (Case company, 2023). This design sets requirements and restrictions for the composition of processed biomass materials and, consequently, for the collection and transportation operations of biomasses as well. Since the case company intends to produce biogas from grass, straws, dry and slurry manure, the logistic operations must be organized in a way that the TS rate within the reactor does not exceed the 15% but comes as close to it as possible.

If the TS rate of the biomass mixture in the plant's reactor exceeds 15%, the biomasses need to be diluted with water before being inserted into the AD process. This dilution incurs avoidable monetary and time costs, making the overall AD process suboptimal. Therefore, to ensure optimal material flow within the biogas plant, the logistic operations should be executed in a manner that maintains a TS rate lower than, but as close as

possible to, 15% within the plant's storage, assuming the AD process and material flows within the plants are daily ongoing processes.

To ensure a suitable TS rate within the AD process, passive drying of biomasses during transportation and warehousing should be examined as a contributing factor. According to van Dyken et al. (2010), the level of moisture within the biomasses is related to their energy content. Therefore, minimizing passive drying of the biomasses to be processed would probably be beneficial for the case company to avoid decreases in the energy content due to passive drying. Thus, passive drying can be seen as a time-critical variable affecting the quality of biomasses in terms of their energy content, and later in the supply chain, the biogas yield. Passive drying of processed biomasses could be beneficial if bioenergy is planned to be produced with a dry AD process (Hadin & Eriksson, 2016). However, since the case's biogas plant is designed to produce biogas with a wet process (Hadin & Eriksson, 2016; Case company, 2023), passive drying of biomasses may have harmful effects on biogas production if the TS rate exceeds 15% due to passive drying. To avoid biomasses exceeding a 15% TS rate, the logistics and transportation of biomasses should be executed as efficiently and quickly as possible, which is also aligned with the existence of time-critical variables affecting biomass quality in terms of the biogas yield.

Factors affecting the utilization rate, later referred to as the AD rate, which represents the degradable fraction of the biomass, i.e., the proportion of the input from which biogas is produced, should also be considered here. Hadin et al. (2016) examined the critical factors affecting the AD of horse manure. According to their study, storage type, storage time, and transport distance from the farm to energy production had impacts on the methane potential and nutrient content of the inspected biomasses. They concluded that the storage time of manure appeared to reduce methane potential and nutrient content through the decomposition of manure, indicating the presence of time-critical variables that affect the quality of horse manure in terms of the biogas production. (Hadin et al. 2016)

A similar conclusion has been presented by Mönch-Tegeder et al. (2013) regarding the time-sensitive factors affecting the biogas potential of horse manure. The storage duration of manure seemed to have a significant decreasing impact on the methane potential of horse manure, reducing the easily degradable fraction of manure and resulting in a suboptimal biogas production process compared to the fresh manure. Manure storage also appeared to contribute to energy losses. (Mönch-Tegeder et al. 2013)

Key time-sensitive factors negatively affecting the methane potential of horse manure and, consequently, biogas yield are passive underlying chemical processes that result in the release of methane and nitrous oxide (Hadin et al. 2016). These passive processes occur during storage and transport, causing emissions and reducing the biogas potential of manure (Hadin et al. 2016). As a result, the production quantities of biogas and biomass utilization rates decrease. Approximately 25% of the total nitrogen is lost during storage (Hadin et al. 2016), indicating that storage and other possible inefficiencies contribute to increased total emissions of the system and a reduced biogas yield.

The storage duration has an impact on the biogas production process itself. Research has shown that storage decreases a fraction of easily degradable compounds within the manure compared to fresh manure, thus reducing the efficiency of the biogas production process. (Hadin et al. 2016) Additionally, it has been noted that the decomposition of dry manure within the AD process progresses more slowly compared to wetter manure (Hadin et al. 2016). Therefore, the effects of passive drying of manures (van Dyken et al. 2010) should be considered and minimized.

Additionally, it was noted that GHG emissions released from manures were at their peak during warm seasons, which was observed as an increase in volatile organic matter, leading to a higher passive decomposition rate of manures (Mönch-Tegeger et al. 2013). The study concluded that long-term storage of manures should be avoided to maximize the economic and environmental benefits of the circular system. This requires the establishment of a flexible, efficient, and resilient logistic system for collecting and transporting the manures to biogas production, ensuring the rapid reuse of manure as a raw material in the biogas production. Continuous development and improvement of the logistic system within the supply chain are necessary to minimize the storage duration of manures as much as possible to achieve the optimal economic and environmental outcomes. (Mönch-Tegeger et al. 2013)

According to the perceptions and conclusions made by van Dyken et al. (2010), Mönch-Tegeger et al. (2013) and Hadin et al. (2016), it can indisputably be stated that time-sensitive variables affecting the quality of manures in terms of their energy potential exist. That is why the logistic system processing them should be as efficient as possible to ensure the maximization of biogas production quantities and the minimization of emissions and waste. These dynamics can also be assumed to apply during the transportation of manures since they are stored within the collection vehicles during the transportation.

These factors affecting methane potential, nutrient content, and emissions generated should also be considered by the case company when planning its logistic operations, as similar dynamics can be expected when transporting other types of manures. To optimize the supply chain of manures and maximize the AD rate of the biogas plant, manures should be collected and transported to the biogas production as quickly as possible, with minimal storage time and total mileage to minimize emissions and costs. However, since achieving a 100% AD rate may be impossible, and some biomasses usually does not degrade within the AD process and results in digestates (Monlau et al. 2015), the processing of digestates should also be planned to maximize their later utilization, which will be discussed in the following subchapter.

2.3.2 Digestates as fertilizers

Another interesting area of the case company's supply chain and its CBMs is the use of digestate, which refers to the fraction of biomass that has not been anaerobically degraded (Monlau et al. 2015). This kind of digestate is typically used as fertilizer. It can be resold back to farmers for their use, thereby recycling nutrients, supporting crop growth, minimizing biomass leakage, and ultimately enhancing the CBE. (Donner et al. 2020) From a logistic optimization perspective, it would be interesting to examine whether the logistic routing of biomasses has an impact on the AD rate of biomass processing. If the quality of the transported biomasses is a time-critical variable that impacts the AD-rate, it can be reasoned that with an optimal solution to the logistic routing problem, the AD process can also be optimized for factors related to the logistic operations. The optimal AD rate for the biogas plant depends on the case-specific factors and should not be tried to be generalized. Case-specific factors include variables such as market prices for biogas and fertilizers, accessibility to customers, and external influences like the number of competing biogas plants.

Based on the findings of van Dyken et al. (2010) and Hadin et al. (2016), discussed in chapter 2.3.1, it can be assumed that there are time-critical variables that affect the quality of manures in terms of their methane potential and nutrient content. Therefore, to maximize the reuse potential of digestates as fertilizers, their nutrient content should be maximized. Thus, the optimal solution for picking up and transporting the biomasses to biogas production also improves the fertilization potential of digestates, highlighting the need to organize the collection and transportation operations of manures from farms to biogas production as effectively and quickly as possible, with minimized storage and transport time, as well as the emissions of the system.

Based on the inefficiencies in the AD process (where not 100% of the biomasses are degraded), it could be reasonable to ask whether it would be more profitable and desirable to sell and use the manures generated on the farms as fertilizer in the first place, instead of first transporting it in and out of the biogas facility? This question becomes relevant when the supply of manure and the demand for manure as a fertilizer are in balance. However, in most cases, the availability of manure is usually higher than the fertilizer needs (Kamilaris & Prenefeta-Boldú, 2021). In addition, it has been found that utilizing surpluses of digestates as fertilizers leads to a lower level of emissions compared to spreading raw manure on fields as a fertilizer (Jensen et al. 2017). Therefore, utilizing digestates as fertilizers instead of raw manures enhances the implementation of the CBE principles through decreased emissions. The type of manure being inspected here is also a relevant question since research results have concluded that the profitability of setting up treatment units to compost manure for later fertilizer use depends on the species of the manure being inspected. Another factor to consider is the season of the review period, as there may be national policies restricting the use of solid manure as a fertilizer during certain times. (Kamilaris & Prenefeta-Boldú, 2021)

However, it should also be considered that transporting manures to be used as fertilizer comes with considerable logistic and transportation costs as well, although their usage decreases the need to use artificial fertilizer inputs (Lessman et al. 2023). It has also been found that the number of harmful pathogens in digestate resulting from the AD process is linked to storage time and other process parameters, such as temperature and the carbon-nitrogen ratio of the feedstock-manure (Nag et al. 2019). There is no reason to question whether pathogens also exist in pure manure, which reduces the attractiveness of both digestate and pure manure for use as fertilizer in the food industry, since the usage of organic materials as fertilizers can contribute to pollution (Lessmann et al. 2023). From this perspective, the most reasonable solution to this question would be to produce as much biogas as possible and, depending on the AD rate of the process, decide whether transporting the resulting digestate is reasonable and cost-effective. The emergence of harmful pathogens should be ensured to be minimized by considering the factors that affect them (Nag et al. 2019). Therefore, by reviewing the economic and environmental costs and benefits of transporting the digestates back to farms, the case company could increase the probability of aligning its operations with the practices of CBE.

2.4 Supply chain of the biogas production

In Figure 4, an example of a circular supply chain is depicted, which bears resemblance to the supply chain employed by the case company. The illustration showcases the utilization of CBMs within this circular supply chain. See page 24 for the illustration. Following that, this section examines the phases occurring in the supply chain and the related terms presented in Figure 4 in detail.

Figure 4. Example illustration of the case company's circular supply chain. For circular bioeconomy supply chain activities, see Ponjavic et al. (2020). For more details about the selected customer, see Jumpanen (2023).

Figure 4 presents the value creation process and supply chain of biomasses initially generated on farms. They are then transported to be used as feedstocks in biogas production, followed by the value realization through profits made from selling the biogas and digestates as fertilizers. The process phases are described as self-explanatory in Figure 4. However, the phases occurring at the biogas facility, which cover the warehouse processes, material flows, and actual biogas production, include certain indicator terms that measure the performance of those phases within the supply chain. The meaning of these indicator terms should be explained. The indicator terms are inventory turnover, delivery time, order point, EOQ, production capacity, MRP, production planning, EPQ, and quality management.

These terms presented above are all closely related to the philosophy of lean production (Demeter & Matyusz, 2011). Lean aims to satisfy customer demand at the highest possible level while minimizing wastes, losses, and other inefficiencies throughout the supply chain. If executed effectively, lean procedures enable lower storage levels and faster inventory turnover, thereby reducing storage costs and waste, and therefore aligning practices with the principles of CBE. (Demeter & Matyusz, 2011)

Since the demand for biogas is assumed to be relatively steady in the case company's operating environment due to the chosen strategic customer (Jumppanen, 2023), and the product portfolio of the biogas plant is narrow, consisting of biogas and digestates sold as fertilizers, the benefits of lean are more achievable, according to Demeter & Matyusz (2011). These benefits within the operation of the supply chain can be achieved by the case company by making wise choices of biomass feedstock suppliers, preferring suppliers with high delivery security and biomass production capacity, as well as aiming for short and predictable delivery times.

However, since real-world supply chain processes are not deterministic and various disruptions may occur within them, planning and operating the supply chain for the biogas production should consider being prepared for feedstock supply disruptions, biogas production stoppages caused by feedstock shortages, and other factors that may lead to production interruptions. Additionally, uncertainty in biogas and fertilizer demand should also be taken into consideration. To prepare for feedstock supply disruptions, it could be beneficial to employ biomass type-specific reorder points and order quantities, ensuring a continuous production process through the use of safety stocks (Sevgen & Sargut, 2019). The determination of order quantities and reorder points should be guided by a model that takes into account case-specific uncertainties in relevant factors, such as demand levels and lead times (Chaharsooghi & Heydari, 2010).

The reorder point establishes a threshold for the storage level of a feedstock, triggering the creation of a new purchase order when the storage level falls below it. When the storage level is below the reorder point, a purchase order with the specified quantity for the feedstock is sent to the supplier. By considering the costs of purchasing, including fixed and logistic costs, storage costs, and the expected demand for the feedstock, the economic order quantity (EOQ) can be defined. This helps determine the optimal order quantity for purchases. (Sevgen & Sargut, 2019) If an optimal order quantity can be defined and utilized, waste, losses, and costs caused by procurement operations could be reduced, thereby enhancing compliance with the principles of CBE. However, the efficient utilization of optimized values for order points and quantities requires commitment from all parties across the supply and demand sides (Chaharsooghi & Heydari, 2010). To ensure the commitment of supply-side actors, models for reorder points and quantities that also incentivize suppliers could be developed. These models incentivize actors on the supply side by providing shared economic benefits through commonly agreed-upon agreements and practices related to the procurement and supply of feedstocks. (Chaharsooghi & Heydari, 2010)

Given that the demand for biomass feedstocks is cyclical and discontinuous due to the long processing time of a feedstock batch within anaerobic digestion (Su et al. 2022), defining and applying reorder points and order quantities for biomass feedstocks could significantly help the case company prepare for feedstock shortages without interrupting biogas production. However, higher storage levels may lead to additional storage costs and feedstock spoilage, reducing the biogas and fertilizer yield of the production process (Hadin et al. 2016). Therefore, the reorder points and order quantities should be defined with careful consideration of all other possible and relevant consequences. This includes determining threshold values for potential acceptable spoilage rate and storage costs.

Although the demand for the biogas produced in the case company's biogas reactor can be assumed to be rather steady and predictable due to the chosen strategic customer (Jumppanen, 2023), unpredictable disruptions may still occur, impacting biogas demand. It should be noted that these potential disruptive impacts on demand, whether negative or positive, should be considered. Regardless, preparation for demand disruptions can be achieved by establishing and maintaining biogas storage facilities near the biogas plant (Jensen et al. 2017; Butemann & Schimmelpfeng, 2020).

Since biogas is unlikely to spoil like feedstock manures, it is reasonable to suggest that the case company prioritize biogas production over storing manures and straws when biogas production is not in progress. This suggestion holds if the costs of biogas and

fertilizer storage are reasonable and acceptable (Jensen et al. 2017). However, it is important to consider that the unit storage cost for biogas may be higher compared to the unit storage cost of feedstocks, as gas has a lower density than feedstocks, requiring more storage space and containers. Once again, the actual decision regarding the prioritization of storing gas and fertilizers with continuous biogas production instead of intentionally maintaining feedstock storage levels should always be made by considering all potential consequences related to total costs, emissions, and biogas and fertilizer nutrient yields. These decisions should align with the case company's production planning and material requirements planning (MRP) processes, which determine the biogas and fertilizer production batch sizes and schedules to meet the expected demand (Stevenson, 2014, pp. 495–515).

MRP is a process carried out in conjunction with production planning, where the material requirements for planned production volume are determined, and upcoming purchase orders are scheduled. Production capacity should be considered alongside production planning and MRP, since it may restrict the production volumes in the time unit, which may lead to oversized feedstock storages, causing pollution and waste. (Stevenson, 2014, pp. 495–515) Differences in biogas yield potential across biomasses to be utilized should also be considered when defining the composition of biomasses for AD. For instance, manures have a lower biogas yield compared to straws (Jensen et al. 2017), indicating that the proportion of manure in the composition should be restricted to achieve the planned biogas production volumes. Alongside material requirements and production planning, the economic production quantity (EPQ) could be determined and utilized to define an economically optimal production batch size for biogas, as well as for digestate as a by-product (Karmakar et al. 2017). EPQ is fundamentally similar to EOQ (Sevgen & Sargut, 2019), which takes into account inventory and fixed costs of production, as well as the demand for biogas and fertilizers. It proposes an optimal batch size for biogas and digestate production. If executed with justification and efficiency, an optimal production schedule resulting from production planning and MRP processes could ultimately improve the economic viability of the biogas plant through decreased production costs (Jensen et al. 2017). This would enable more resource allocation towards improving the practices that enhance CBE.

Alongside production planning, potential incentive structures for the biogas production set by the regulators should also be considered if they exist. If the incentive structure enables it, it may be reasonable and economically more viable to schedule production of biogas for times of high market prices for electricity, while favoring the storage of biogas and fertilizers during times of low market prices (Butemann & Schimmelpfeng, 2020).

This would be the case for the case company's biogas plant if they decided to let markets price biogas and fertilizers to be delivered. However, due to the chosen strategic customer (Jumppanen, 2023), the prices for biogas are probably set by a mutual agreement. Additional costs caused by recurrent stopping and starting combined heat and power units would result in avoidable costs and wear and tear (Butemann & Schimmelpfeng, 2020), which may decrease profits and unnecessarily commit critical resources of the biogas plant, instead of using those resources to improve the practices enhancing CBE. However, if incentive structures of this kind are found to exist, and the biogas and fertilizers are sold at market prices, the case company should consider this as a relevant factor while planning its biogas production, since it is possible to increase revenues and minimize additional costs caused by the flexible production of biogas (Butemann & Schimmelpfeng, 2020).

The last concept to be explained is quality management. Although it is illustrated as being related to the warehouse and production phases of the supply chain in Figure 4, it should be noted that quality management practices should be considered and executed throughout all phases of the supply chain. In the context of processing biomass materials consisting of manures, grass, and straws, the quality management practices to be implemented should focus on the inactivation of harmful pathogens within the manures and digestates (Nag et al. 2019). If harmful pathogens still exist in digestate to be reused as fertilizer, the spreading of serious illnesses may follow as a consequence, especially if digestates are used as a fertilizer in industries producing food for humans and animals (Liu et al. 2008; Kinyua et al. 2016). The pathogens have the potential to spread through air, water, and direct contact, which highlights the need for careful treatment of manures and digestates. (Kinyua et al. 2016; Nag et al. 2019)

However, there are ways to increase pathogen inactivation throughout the AD process by setting up process parameters to create conditions that increase the probability of inactivation (Nag et al. 2019). High process temperature significantly contributes to pathogen inactivation (Manyi-Loh et al. 2013; Nag et al. 2019). The biogas production lead time, or hydraulic retention time (HRT) in other words, also has an impact on pathogen inactivation. Depending on the composition of the biomass to be digested, an HRT of 12 to 35 days could contribute the most to pathogen inactivation as well as biogas yield. Other important factors to consider in decreasing the pathogen count are maintaining a high organic loading rate (OLR) throughout the AD process and pasteurization of materials to be processed. (Sakar et al. 2009; Nag et al. 2019)

2.5 Success and risk factors of the biogas supply chain

The implementation of CBMs within the case company's supply chain involves additional success and risk factors worth noting. Donner et al. (2021) analyzed critical success and risk factors for CBMs that valorize agricultural biomasses and side-flows. From the perspectives of logistic optimization and AD, it should be noted that the outputs of the biogas plant and the efficiency of the logistic operations may be influenced by the need to transport and process different types of biomasses and by-products (Donner et al. 2021). From a logistic perspective, this is critically important as it can impose restrictions on transporting certain materials together, leading to significant impacts on logistics planning and costs. Depending on the TS rate within the plant's storage and production, production may be disrupted if water dilutions are required to reach TS lower than 15 %, decreasing the efficiency of biogas production and restricting it from reaching its full potential. Thus, co-transporting of materials should always be utilized when required and possible from the perspectives of logistics and production management, but also in terms of emissions. It was found by Yu et al. (2023) that co-distribution of straw and manure contributes most to GHG mitigation.

The processing capacity of the biogas plant should also be balanced with the material input from the logistic system. As noted by Donner et al. (2021), high storage capacity for feedstock located nearby the AD processing system may serve as a critical success factor if the biomass to be processed can be stored. However, this incurs storage costs for the case company, requiring analysis and optimization of the balance between storage capacity and delivery times within the logistic system. It is important to consider the possible time sensitivity of the quality of biomasses to be stored, as their accumulation can lead to biomass spoilage and decrease the facility's AD-rate. From this, it can be concluded that with an optimal solution to the logistic routing problem, the utilization rates of biomasses can also be improved, as their quality in terms of methane potential and nutrient content is assumed to be a time-critical variable, as found in the case of horse manure by Hadin et al. (2016). This is intuitive, since if the quality decreases over time, so does the amount of material to be valorized. This means that with an optimal solution to the logistic problem, pollution of materials can also be decreased.

When balancing production capacity, logistics and warehouse management, it should be also noted that the availability of side-streams valorized through AD can be affected by seasonality (Donner et al. 2021). Thus, depending on the magnitude of technological investments in production capacity and valorization rates of processed materials, it should be reviewed what types of materials it is most reasonable to valorize in different seasons. A probable suggestion would be to valorize only manures during the winter and

inspect the costs and benefits of valorizing straws alongside manures during the summer. On the other hand, since the grass and straw are baled in the fields, their collection is permitted throughout the year, although they are accumulated only during the summer. However, making valid recommendations to utilize only a selected group of biomasses in specific periods would require further and more detailed analysis, which is excluded from this study. The collection and utilization of all biomasses of interest are assumed to be continuous, although the peculiarities in their accumulation dynamics are taken into consideration.

The geographical distribution of biomasses and side-streams to be picked up should also be noted as planning the logistic operations. Agricultural wastes and side-streams have varying quality and limited volume depending on the farm (Donner et al. 2021), making it more appealing to pick up biomasses from specific farms. Therefore, farms with high quality and volume of biomasses should be recognized and establish strategic partnerships with their owners. If the required biomass is picked up from farms with high volume and quality, it follows that the need for logistic operators to pick up biomass from several farms decreases. Thus, it can be reasoned that the total mileage driven by the logistic operators decreases, indicating lower fuel consumption and emissions caused by the vehicles. Efficient resource consumption and the minimization of emissions should remain as key design principles when planning logistic operations. This is because the total contribution of bioenergy production systems to the ecological footprint has been questioned by Wang et al. (2020), who concluded that biomass-based energy production increased the ecological footprint of G7 countries. Therefore, aligning practices with CBE principles, such as minimizing emissions and maximizing resource usage, should not be taken for granted. Instead, the pursuit of these practices should guide all related decision-making processes in planning the logistic operations as well.

2.6 Synthesis of literature review

Based on the previously presented literature review, it can be generally stated that the profitable and efficient utilization of CBMs requires in-depth analysis of the prevailing market, industry, and company-related factors and dynamics. Due to the broad set of ways to minimize resource consumption and maximize their utilization, the material flows and the processes affected by them should be defined and well-known before choosing the parameters of the CBM to be utilized.

However, in the context of the case company and the CBE, it seems that the selection of actors and processes in the supply chain and processing technologies to valorize biomass materials through bioenergy production are justified. These selections aim to

achieve aligning practices with the principles of CBE, which include reducing emissions, minimizing costs, maximizing biomass utilization, and enhancing sustainability by proposing bio-based energy alternatives.

In planning the logistic operations related to transporting, storing, and utilizing biomasses such as manures, grasses and straws collected from nearby farms, the case company should optimize its supply chain. This optimization involves optimizing the transportation of biomasses from farms to the biogas plant, as well as warehouse and production management. The optimization of transportation logistics for biomasses is thoroughly examined in this study. Additionally, the examination covers monitoring stock levels of feedstocks and their consumption within the biogas production process. However, other factors related to warehouse management and production control are excluded from the analysis. The costs caused by the logistic system may have subsequent implications for endangering the achievement of aligning practices with the principles of CBE by consuming the company's resources, namely money, on unproductive operations such as logistics. These resources could be better invested in funding research on more advanced bioprocessing techniques and practices, ultimately enhancing circularity itself.

Based on the literature review and synthesis, a theoretical framework was designed to highlight the factors of the biogas supply chain that need to be improved and can be enhanced with developed data processing and dynamic optimization tools. These tools will be examined in the following chapter, and the framework is presented below.

Figure 5. Framework of the factors within the biogas supply chain that can be improved with developed methods.

Optimizing complicated supply chains, such as that of the case company, often requires the use of analytical tools to model and optimize their functioning. Such tools have been developed in earlier studies for municipal solid waste (Das & Bhattacharyya, 2015), broad regional supply chain consisting of multiple products and feedstocks (Balaman et al. 2018), to recognize key performance indicators of poultry manure supply chain (Ponjavic et al. 2020), to optimize the logistics of straightforward utilization of manures as fertilizers without the biogas production (Kamilaris & Prenafeta-Boldú, 2021), to optimize combined biomass flows of straws and manures (Yu et al. 2023), utilizing wood biomasses in bioenergy production (Shabani & Sowlati, 2013), and to optimize supply chains of biofuel production (Zhang et al. 2013; Huang et al. 2014).

However, these kinds of tools model the case-specific factors, such as the scope of modeling, the number of actors, the types of materials and flows being inspected, etc., in detail. Analyzing at a detailed level is a prerequisite for obtaining reliable research results, which limits the applicability of models developed under different circumstances in the context of the case company in this study. Dynamically optimizing the logistic routing of transporting biomass side-flows from farms to the case company's biogas plant requires the development of a new model that considers case-specific factors relevant to that context. This model development and research methodology will be examined in the next chapter.

3 LOGISTIC ROUTING OPTIMIZATION OF BIOMASS SIDE-FLOWS – METHODOLOGY

The research methodology of this study is described in this chapter. First, the research design and strategy are established by discussing the goals, purpose, and research process of the study. Secondly, the optimization problem of this study is presented at a conceptual level. Then, the data and its collection method used in this study are presented. In the third subchapter, the data processing phases are presented in detail with illustrative examples. After data processing, the model in which the processed data is to be used is presented. The model covers the simulation approach to logistic routing optimization and the utilization of the genetic algorithm within it. Lastly, the validity and reliability of the methodology are reviewed.

3.1 Research design and strategy

This study aims to scan the biomass potentials that could potentially be utilized by the case company, provide information on cost-effective selection of biomass pick-up sites, and propose an optimal plan to implement logistic routing operations related to the collection and transportation of biomass side-flows for the bioenergy production at the case company's biogas plant. It simultaneously considers the prevailing restrictions, opportunities and dynamics related to the CBE that were analyzed in the literature review of the study, presented in the previous section. These prevailing conditions cover factors such as the general principles of CBE, which aim to minimize waste, emissions, and costs while maximizing the utilization rates of agricultural wastes such as manures and side-flows of grasses and straws. Case-specific conditions are also considered, such as the restriction of the TS rate within the biogas production and targeted input values for the biomasses to be processed at the biogas plant.

Additionally, the study aims to produce basic information for a possible paradigm shift in the field, supported by the study's results. The current practice in the field of not dynamically optimizing the logistic routing operations may be questioned if the study's results conclude that dynamic optimization could yield significant cost savings. Dynamic optimization in this context encompasses the dynamic processes of biomass accumulation, movements, and decisions made by logistic operators, as well as the consideration of potential time-critical variables related to the quality of biomass. Therefore, by achieving the goals of the study, this study and its results could ultimately enable CBMs in the

context of the CBE more effectively, produce valuable information for the case company's decision-makers, and explain how the case company could reach its targets of operating its CBMs effectively.

This study utilizes both quantitative and qualitative methods, with a focus on quantitative methods. Data modeling, processing, and the utilization of processed data in simulation schemes to optimize logistic routing are self-evidently quantitative methods since they involve measurable, numerical variables (Saunders et al. 2019). The aim of these quantitative methods is to seek objectively undisputed results within the scope of the study's assumptions, highlighting positivism as a research philosophy of the study. However, since these quantitative methods involve choices and decision-making by the creators of the methodologies, it could be argued that this study also utilizes qualitative methods, ultimately making it a multi-method study (Saunders et al. 2019).

For instance, since the original data required significant processing before being utilized in the simulation scheme, as seen in the following subchapters 3.3 and 3.4, the researcher made various choices regarding quantitative data procession methods. One such choice was the utilization of the K-Means clustering algorithm to model the pick-up sites (Jeffares, 2019; Magiya, 2019; scikit-learn developers, 2023). Although these quantitative methods were validated with other quantitative methods, such as plotting the pre-processed data and calculating WCSS for clustering (Saji, 2023), the initial choice of the method was determined qualitatively by the researcher.

The study is conducted with a constructive research approach in accordance with the principles of positivism and pragmatism (Saunders et al. 2019). By its nature, the study is an applied practical research endeavor, aiming to solve a problem and provide guidance on how the collection and transportation of biomass side-flows should be executed within the case company. The problem-solving nature of the study, along with the researcher's qualitative choices of quantitative methods, emphasizes pragmatism. Furthermore, the utilization of precise and measurable variables in the simulation and optimization processes highlights the role of positivism.

The time horizon of the study is cross-sectional, as the simulated and optimized results are generated within a short timeframe from June 2023 to August 2023 (Saunders et al. 2019). It should be noted that the original biomass data, described in chapter 3.3, originated from a longer perspective, with each dataset including annual data. However, this is not relevant in terms of the time horizon of the study, as the original biomass data is modeled as pick-up sites in the simulation scheme, and the simulation itself was run in a short timeframe from June 2023 to August 2023, resulting in the perception that the

result data was generated within a short timeframe. The simulation period itself for biomass accumulation and logistic routing is one year, resulting in a proposal for routing plans on a yearly level.

The research process is as follows. The research topic was identified and defined through the collaboration of research organizations, namely HAMK Smart, HAMK Bio, and LuKe. This was based on a research problem presented by a case company planning to establish a biogas plant. The research problem can be summarized as a question of how and from where the case company should collect biomasses for biogas production, while considering the production process restrictions and the principles of CBE. Three research questions were created to address the research problem, as presented in chapter 1.3. The principles of CBE and production process restrictions were discovered through a literature review in the second chapter of the paper.

The data used in this study consists of geospatial datasets for various types of biomasses located in Finland (LuKe, 2023). The data collection, description, and processing are explained in detail in subchapters 3.3 and 3.4. The data was used to scan the biomass distribution in the nearby areas of the facility and to generate appropriate simulation schemes by modeling the biomass pick-up sites from the datasets. Based on the generated biomass pick-up sites for a total of 9 biomass types, a simulation scheme was defined, and logistic routing was optimized by running the simulation multiple times (Niemitalo & Ekkerman, 2022; Eloranta, 2023b). The optimization was achieved by applying a genetic algorithm (GA) to minimize a cost function defined within the simulation scheme (Gracia et al. 2014; Katoch et al. 2021).

The simulation scheme, which simulates the circumstances of the optimization problem described in section 3.2, was defined through discussions with experts from HAMK Bio, LuKe, HAMK Smart, and the case company. These discussions included considerations of various factors, such as the differing dynamics of biomass accumulation depending on the biomass type and the varying dynamics of collecting different biomasses, which have implications for the cost function. Additionally, differences in warehouse capacity assumptions for relevant farms were considered. For instance, the warehouse capacity for grasses and straws stored in the field was assumed to be infinite, while for manures, it was assumed to be the total sum accumulated within a year as dictated by the law (Government Decree on the Restriction of Discharge of Nitrates From Agriculture into Waters 2000/931 § 4).

The results and their compliance with the restrictions of CBE and the biogas production process were reviewed through post-analysis. For example, the proportion of dry matter

in the reactor producing biogas had to be kept below a given rate, which could be analyzed post-simulation to determine if the condition was met. The results were then analyzed and discussed among experts from HAMK and LuKe, and the discussion of results and key findings of the study are presented in the fifth chapter of the paper.

3.2 The problem of biomass routing and biogas production

The optimization problem of this study combines and expands upon elements from the vehicle routing problem (VRP), which can be considered a generalization of the classical traveling salesman problem (TSP) for multiple operators (Bochtis & Sørensen, 2009). It also incorporates elements from the biomass collection problem (BCP) (Gracia et al. 2014). The collection points, modeled as pickup sites within the routing problem, and the level of their content, needed to be calculated from geo-spatial biomass datasets as outlined in Chapters 3.3 and 3.4. However, the development of pickup sites was not optimized within the genetic algorithm itself, resulting in their exclusion from the actual optimization problem. Therefore, the data processing presented in Chapters 3.3 and 3.4 can be considered a solution for BCP. In this context, the pickup sites and their dynamics are assumed and taken as given within the optimization problem.

The elements expanding the VRP encompass the dynamic accumulation of biomasses at pickup sites, as well as modeling their consumption within the biogas plant. Another expansion of the VRP involves not allowing a vehicle to visit certain sites, as the vehicle's type determines the sites it is supposed to visit. Modeling of biomass consumption involves assuming a continuous biogas production process on a daily basis, with discrete consumption of biomasses from the plant's storage. Therefore, the optimization problem of this study is referred to as the Biomass Routing and Biogas Production Problem (BRBPP). BRBPP is described at a conceptual level within this subchapter, and the developed methodology aimed at solving it is presented in Chapter 3.5

In VRP, a fleet of vehicles is supposed to visit a fixed number of collection points, with each point being visited exactly once. The optimization problem in VRP is to find the routing that minimizes the total distance driven while satisfying the requirement of visiting each point exactly once. (Gracia et al. 2014) Vehicles have capacity levels that pickups should not exceed during a route, and a route starts from and ends at a depot site (Bochtis & Sørensen, 2010). A duration of a route, including travel time and time spent at sites, is bounded to preset limit (Berger & Barkaoui, 2003). In BRBPP, the number of visits at each site is not restricted to one, as the number of visits is determined by the time window of the problem. To elaborate further, the number of visits at a site depends on the number of vehicles allowed to visit a site, the assumed time window, and the

problem parameters that define the duration of each visit at the site. The duration of a route must not exceed the duration of a single work shift.

VRP assumes that collection points are static, meaning that the amount of mass that can be picked up there remains constant over time. Once the pickup operation is completed, the site does not need to be visited further, as the pickable mass does not accumulate over time. (Bochtis & Sørensen, 2009) In BRBPP, biomasses are assumed to accumulate at sites, implying that a site may need to be revisited once it has been emptied. Depending on the type of biomass accumulating within the site, the accumulation process may be linear and discretely continuous on a daily basis. Alternatively, it could be discontinuous, with biomass accumulation observed only on random days. In this case, the amount of accumulation is greater compared to linear accumulation, resulting in what is known as a biomass “jump”. At sites where the accumulation process is discretely continuous, the maximum storage capacity is assumed. If the site's mass level exceeds this capacity, additional storage costs are incurred. Therefore, it can be argued that BRBPP combines and modifies elements of the vehicle routing problem with time windows (VRPTW) as well, where the demand of a node must be satisfied within a given time window (Bochtis & Sørensen, 2010). In BRBPP, sites are not obligated to be visited precisely within the time windows defined by the site. However, the longer the visit to a site takes, the more possible additional storage costs may accumulate over time, contributing to the total costs of the solution.

A significant expansion of the BRBPP, which contributes significantly to the increased complexity of the problem, involves the assumed biogas production process that consumes biomasses picked up and transported to the biogas plant by the vehicles. In TSP, VRP, and VRPTW, the depot is assumed solely as the starting and ending point of the routes, with no significant attributes of its own (Berger & Barkaoui, 2003; Bochtis & Sørensen, 2009; Bochtis & Sørensen, 2010; Gracia et al. 2014). In BRBPP, the biogas plant is represented as the depot, with its storage levels required to fulfill the resource demand of the biogas production. This production process involves consuming biomasses from the storage on a daily basis. If the storage runs out, a production stoppage and significant additional costs emerge. The composition of the stored biomasses must stay within certain thresholds, as the TS rate of the organic material to be anaerobically digested must not exceed 15% within a wet process (Hadin & Eriksson, 2016). If the weighted average of TS in storage exceeds 15%, dilution water must be added to achieve an appropriate TS ratio, resulting in additional costs to the system. The biomasses have targeted input values on an annual level, and plant's storages have capacities representing these targeted values. If a storage level exceeds its capacity, additional

costs are incurred. Similarly, if the total amount of biomass imported during the year surpasses the targeted annual input, additional costs are incurred in the form of unnecessary imports.

The dynamic accumulation of biomasses at the sites transforms the BRBPP into a dynamic optimization problem (Liu et al. 2019). For instance, a decision to visit a certain site a week later instead of immediately affects the total costs of a solution, as this decision could ultimately impact the occurrence of a production stoppage at the biogas plant if storage runs out. This is due to the choice of early site visit with a lower level of biomass to be collected, rather than visiting a site with a greater level of biomass and postponing the visit to the initial site for the following week. Additional storage costs caused by exceeding the site's storage capacity could also arise, depending on whether the initial site was visited immediately or not.

The illustration of the BRBPP is presented in Figure 6; refer to page 39 for that. The illustration highlights various types of pickup sites and vehicles. The scenario depicted in the illustration can be considered a starting point for a typical day within the simulation period, providing an example of a partial solution to BRBPP. At the beginning of each day, every vehicle is assigned a route, which is essentially a list of locations to be visited throughout that day. A vehicle's route may also be empty, indicating that no transportation is required for that vehicle during that day.

The solution encompasses routing information for each vehicle for every day of the simulation period. For example, if the simulation period is set to last 251 days and routing is calculated for 9 vehicles, the BRBPP solution includes routing details for those 9 vehicles over the coming 251 days. The solution is derived through optimization facilitated by the GA, which simulates the system with generated routing proposals and calculates the costs incurred with the given routing. The cost function is shown in the lower right corner of Figure 6; a more comprehensive analysis of it is provided in Chapter 3.5.2.

Figure 6. An example illustration of a partial solution to the Biomass Routing and Biogas Production Problem (BRBPP).

As can be detected from the cost function presented in the Figure 6, the value of a cost function is determined by multiple variables. The presence of multiple variables affecting to the costs of a solution proposal alters the BRBPP multi-dimensional optimization problem, whose solutions can be sought by multi-objective optimization methods (Jozefowicz et al. 2008; Baños et al. 2013; Banasik et al. 2017). The difference is fundamental in comparison with the classical VRP, whose solutions minimize the total distance driven by the operators with the requirement of visiting each node once, thus being a single-objective optimization problem (Jozefowicz et al. 2008; Baños et al. 2013). By incorporating multiple cost terms, which are objective variables to be minimized through optimized routing, the optimization of biomass side-flows within a circular supply chain allows us to discover more comprehensive solutions. These solutions consider the relevant factors that affect costs in the system, thereby enhancing the overall efficiency of the supply chain. (Jozefowicz et al. 2008; Baños et al. 2013; Banasik et al. 2017).

The cost function presented in Figure 6, examined in detail in Chapter 3.5.2, aims to find a logistical routing for a simulation period that optimizes the operation of the biogas production supply chain, from the farms to the biogas reactor. This optimization should mitigate production interruptions in the biogas production due to resource shortages, minimize the consumption of dilution water in production, prevent overflows and excessive visits to the facility. This can be achieved through route planning that simultaneously minimizes driving distances (and wrong visits), reduces overtime for drivers, and ensures sufficient storage capacity on a farm-specific basis for biomass production.

3.3 Data collection and description

The data used in this study was collected from LuKe's Biomassa-atlas (LuKe, 2023). The Biomassa-atlas provides geospatial datasets for various types of biomasses located in Finland. The methodology used in creating and calculating Biomassa-atlas's datasets is described in detail by Luostarinen et al. (2017). The datasets include information on the year of dataset collection, biomass type, mass in tons, and location coordinates for each biomass point. Location coordinates for each mass point were given as multipolygons, including corner points of the area covering the biomass. The coordinates were initially given in the EUREF-FIN coordinate system and were later transformed to the WGS84 coordinate system as part of the data processing. These corner points were used to calculate an average point of areas. Hence, average points were approximated to include an area's mass, to enable processing biomasses as unique points. An example of the unprocessed data is illustrated in Figure 7.

Year	Type	Mass	Area
2021	Sivuvirta: Olki	171.17503574877458	MULTIPOLYGON (((213000 6735000, 212000 6735000, 212000 6736000, 213000 6736000, 213000 6735000)))
2021	Sivuvirta: Olki	95.57233996105636	MULTIPOLYGON (((212000 6735000, 211000 6735000, 211000 6736000, 212000 6736000, 212000 6735000)))
2021	Sivuvirta: Olki	65.31039001374523	MULTIPOLYGON (((211000 6735000, 210000 6735000, 210000 6736000, 211000 6736000, 211000 6735000)))
2021	Sivuvirta: Olki	29.159214785914504	MULTIPOLYGON (((210000 6735000, 209000 6735000, 209000 6736000, 210000 6736000, 210000 6735000)))
2021	Sivuvirta: Olki	102.75545843264452	MULTIPOLYGON (((209000 6735000, 208000 6735000, 208000 6736000, 209000 6736000, 209000 6735000)))
2021	Sivuvirta: Olki	56.47838019788172	MULTIPOLYGON (((208000 6735000, 207000 6735000, 207000 6736000, 208000 6736000, 208000 6735000)))
2021	Sivuvirta: Olki	20.863907590051603	MULTIPOLYGON (((207000 6735000, 206000 6735000, 206000 6736000, 207000 6736000, 207000 6735000)))
2021	Sivuvirta: Olki	16.291681425734275	MULTIPOLYGON (((206000 6735000, 205000 6735000, 205000 6736000, 206000 6736000, 206000 6735000)))
2021	Sivuvirta: Olki	7.10984628536991	MULTIPOLYGON (((205000 6735000, 204000 6735000, 204000 6736000, 205000 6736000, 205000 6735000)))
2021	Sivuvirta: Olki	54.714957257391085	MULTIPOLYGON (((204000 6735000, 203000 6735000, 203000 6736000, 204000 6736000, 204000 6735000)))
2021	Sivuvirta: Olki	93.42134309873094	MULTIPOLYGON (((203000 6735000, 202000 6735000, 202000 6736000, 203000 6736000, 203000 6735000)))
2021	Sivuvirta: Olki	4.416107269677052	MULTIPOLYGON (((202000 6735000, 201000 6735000, 201000 6736000, 202000 6736000, 202000 6735000)))
2021	Sivuvirta: Olki	33.06942406654538	MULTIPOLYGON (((201000 6735000, 200000 6735000, 200000 6736000, 201000 6736000, 201000 6735000)))
2021	Sivuvirta: Olki	96.41755163128677	MULTIPOLYGON (((200000 6735000, 199000 6735000, 199000 6736000, 200000 6736000, 200000 6735000)))
2021	Sivuvirta: Olki	51.24894953309141	MULTIPOLYGON (((199000 6735000, 198000 6735000, 198000 6736000, 199000 6736000, 199000 6735000)))

Figure 7. An example of the form of unprocessed data.

All datasets collected and used in this study were initially in a consistent, unified format, as illustrated previously. However, the datasets related to manures were on the municipal level, while the datasets for grass and straw were more detailed. The selection of datasets was conducted with case-by-case consideration to align the types of biomasses inspected in the datasets with the case company's intentions regarding the types of biomasses to be collected and used for the biogas production. The opinions of LuKe's experts were also taken into account regarding the types of biomasses that the case company is likely willing and able to utilize. The datasets chosen, processed, and utilized in this study included slurry manure of bovines and pigs stored in animal shelters in the years 2015 and 2016, dry manure of horses, bovines, poultry, and pigs stored in storage facilities in 2016, and side-streams of straw, grass, and silage grass generated in 2021.

3.4 Data procession

The data processing tool was developed and written in Python as part of this study. The source code for the tool is publicly available (Eloranta, 2023a). The tool was developed to map the biomasses located nearby the biogas plant, determining the extent to which biomass potentials from surrounding areas could meet the resource needs of the plant's annual production capacity. Additionally, the tool aimed to identify and approximate potential and optimal pick-up sites for logistic operators, from which biomasses could be collected and transported to the plant for use in biogas production.

The pre-processed data was initially plotted to validate its correctness, including loading, transforming, and averaging operations. Figure 8 illustrates an example of this phase, where the x- and y-axes represent the coordinates of the biomass points. The points are colored based on their mass, highlighting areas with higher biomass density. The color bar on the right side of the diagram represents the scaling system for coloring the points.

Figure 8. An example of the data pre-processing phase.

After data validation, the datasets were filtered to include only biomasses located within a 50-kilometer radius from the plant's location. The cutoff value for the 50-kilometer radius was set because it appeared that biomasses within this range could easily meet the plant's resource demand. Expert opinions from LuKe and HAMK were also considered, along with the case company's interests regarding the resource demand levels. Euclidean distances were calculated for each point, and biomasses that were further than the chosen cutoff value were filtered out from the datasets. The accuracy of the distance calculations and filtering operations was validated by plotting the remaining data once again. An example of this phase of data processing is illustrated in Figure 9 below.

Figure 9. An example of the filtering phase in data processing.

The remaining parts of the datasets were subjected to the unsupervised learning method, the KMeans clustering algorithm, to identify reasonable subareas (Jeffares, 2019; Magiya, 2019; scikit-learn developers, 2023). Approximations from these subareas were later modeled as pick-up sites in logistic simulation and optimization. The uneven geographical distribution of biomasses was taken into account during clustering by duplicating biomass points based on their masses. Mass coefficients were derived accordingly for duplicating points. This duplication was necessary because Sklearn's KMeans clustering algorithm does not consider weights in its clustering; it only considers coordinates without weight coefficients.

The k value used for clustering was validated using the Elbow Method (Saji, 2023). The idea behind the Elbow Method is to cluster the dataset with varying numbers of cluster centers (k) and find the optimal value for k that minimizes the WCSS (within-cluster sum of squares). The optimal k is a value that is small enough to enable efficient calculations, yet large enough that further increasing k would not significantly minimize the WCSS (Saji, 2023). By plotting the WCSS as a function of k , a figure in the form of an elbow is formed, and the optimal k can be located at the elbow. An example of this validation is

presented in Figure 10, which was generated using the same dataset as the previous examples.

Figure 10. An example of the Elbow method in validating the number of clusters.

As can be seen in Figure 10, the WCSS has dramatically decreased as the number of clusters reached 25, approaching almost zero with 100 clusters. However, since these clusters will later be modeled as biomass pick-up sites in logistic simulation (i.e., farms), and the data being used is not farm-specific, it is important to choose the number of clusters cautiously. Additionally, it can be assumed that within a 50 km radius of the biogas facility located in Kanta-Häme, there are more than 25 farms. To ensure that the number of clusters more realistically represents the number of farms in the relevant area, the k value was initially set to 200 for clustering. This decision results in heavier computation but provides a more realistic modeling scheme with a very low WCSS value.

An example of the initial clustering of biomass data within a 50 km radius, using 200 clusters, is presented in Figure 11. It is important to note that the unit of mass was converted to truckloads, assuming that 45 tons are equivalent to one truckload. Additionally, the masses were transformed to a logarithmic scale to enhance the visualization of biomass potentials for the case company. This allows for a better understanding of where the biomasses should be collected and from how far away to meet the resource demand.

In Figure 11, each point located within a colored sub-area represents the weighted central point of that sub-area, which includes all points related to the same cluster. Thus, the colored sub-areas represent clusters in Figure 11's visualization. The intensity of a color of the central point indicates the total amount of biomass within the cluster area.

These kinds of points will be modeled as pick-up sites, assuming that farmers within a cluster area will collect the biomasses and deliver them to the pick-up site for the logistic operator to retrieve.

Figure 11. An example of the initial clustering phase in data processing.

After the initial clustering presented in Figure 11, it was noted that the biomass resource demands for the case company's plant could be easily satisfied within a 50 km radius. The case company set the target input value for grasses and straws at 28,000 tons per year (Tampio, 2023), and it can be seen from Figure 11 that the biomass potentials of straws alone could theoretically meet the requirements. Similarly, with manures, the target value was set at 14,000 tons (Tampio, 2023), leading to similar conclusions. Due to the abundant occurrence of biomasses within the 50 km radius, the number of clusters was reduced to enable more efficient computation later on. It can be intuitively concluded that collecting biomasses as close to the facility as possible would be more cost-efficient, as it would reduce the total kilometers driven. Based on these observations and conclusions, a methodology for thinning the clusters was developed and implemented.

The thinning methodology utilized divides the initially clustered dataset of a 50 km radius area into 5 tires, with each tire having a thickness of 10 km. Then, the new desired value for k within each tire was calculated by dividing the number of clusters originally in the tire by a divisor coefficient raised to the power of the tire's sequence number. With the new value of k for each tire, the biomasses within the tire's area were clustered again, resulting in a lower total number of clusters. As a result, the number of clusters near the plant were thinned the least, while those furthest away were thinned the most. An example of the results of the thinning method described here is presented in Figure 12 below.

Figure 12. An example of the methodology of cluster thinning.

After thinning the clusters, the number of clusters was further reduced to enable more efficient computation. It appeared that the combined masses of different biomasses would exceed the targeted input values of the case company based on their resource demand. In this phase, the number of clusters was reduced by identifying the nearest clusters to meet the yearly biomass resource demand. Clusters that remained above the resource needs were filtered from the data. This filtering procedure was implemented for all biomass datasets, resulting in a significantly lower number of clusters to be calculated. At the same time, it ensured the adequacy of biomasses for the demand, considering

multiple grass, straw, and manure datasets. An example of the resulting clusters from this phase of data processing is presented in Figure 13 in page 48 in unified form with previous figures, and in Figure 14 in format of plotting cluster points within actual map format after transporting datapoints to GEOJSON format.

After calculating the nearest clusters for each biomass type, the resulting datasets were combined to be used in simulation and optimization. It should be noted that the resulting datasets included information about the biomass type, thus ensuring that no information was lost when combining the datasets. The combination of datasets is visualized in Figure 15 in page 49, where the color of each point represents the biomass type.

Figure 13. An example of the nearest clusters to fulfil resource needs.

Figure 14. An example of the nearest clusters plotted within a map.

Figure 15. Pick-up sites approximated from biomass datasets.

The combined dataset, visualized in Figure 15, which consists of pick-up sites for each biomass type, was then imported into GeoJSON format to be used in simulation and optimization. The methodology for logistic routing simulation and dynamic optimization is described in the following section 3.5.

3.5 Model development

The models used for simulation and optimization in this study were based on the previous work of Niemitalo and Ekkerman (2022). They contributed significantly to the development of the model by implementing simulation schemes and the GA for routing optimization. The models implemented by Niemitalo and Ekkerman (2022) were further developed for this study to align the models with case-specific factors, such as operating in the context of CBE and simulating the transportation of biomasses to be used as a resource in the biogas production.

The simulation and optimization tool developed by Niemitalo and Ekkerman (2022) simulates the accumulation of waste at multiple collection sites, referred to as pickup sites. Each pickup site has a unique capacity, current state, geographical coordinates, daily growth rate, and the accumulation follows a linear pattern (Niemitalo & Ekkerman, 2022). In the context of this study and CBE, the adjustments were implemented for the attributes of pickup sites. These adjustments include, for instance, implementing an alternative accumulation model for grasses and straws. More of these adjustments are discussed in the following subchapters 3.5.1 and 3.5.2.

The simulation scheme includes logistic operators, i.e., vehicles, whose mission is to collect waste from the pickup sites and transport it to depot sites. A number of vehicles and geographical coordinates are defined for each depot. Vehicles have attributes such as load capacity, current load, current location, routes to drive, the duration of a shift, the proportion of break time during the shift, and the constant duration for the pickup operation. When a vehicle's load reaches its capacity, the vehicle must return to the depot to unload the collected waste. (Niemitalo & Ekkerman, 2022) The behavior of the logistic operators was also adjusted for this study. For instance, the assumption of a constant duration for the pickup operation was rejected, and the duration of a pickup operation was modeled to consist of two factors: a constant one that represents the setting time required for connecting the equipment within a pickup site, and a factor that is linearly dependent on the amount of waste to be collected. Other case-specific adjustments implemented in the model are described in detail in the following subchapters 3.5.1 and 3.5.2.

Transportation traffic is simulated for a given period of days, which is defined by the user in the simulation scheme's configuration. The type of simulation is process-based discrete event simulation, which is implemented in Python using SimPy (Team SimPy, 2020). The optimizer is implemented in C++ for faster calculations, and, as a result, it uses the C++ implementation of the same simulation model, SimCpp20 (Schütz, 2021). The traffic is simulated with the routes optimized by the GA utilizing SimCpp20. A route is a list of locations for a vehicle for each day. The optimized routes are generated by minimizing a cost function that depends on the routing. (Niemitalo & Ekkerman, 2022) The variables of the initial cost function implemented by Niemitalo and Ekkerman (2022) were fuel consumption, which was derived from kilometers driven by vehicles, overtime work, and daily penalties for overfull pickup sites. The cost function used within the study's biogas case included some additional variables that were implemented and used to consider relevant case-specific factors, such as the dynamics of the biogas production and resource consumption. The cost function utilized in this study is presented in subchapter 3.5.2.

The distances and travel times between the pickup sites and other locations were collected by utilizing a routing API (openrouteservice, 2023), which returns distance and duration matrices for the given geographical coordinates. These matrices were used to calculate the costs of alternative routing proposals generated by the GA. Routing proposals are ranked by the GA based on their costs, while the minimization of costs is preferred when generating new routing proposals through the GA. (Niemitalo & Ekkerman, 2022)

3.5.1 Simulation approach to biomass routing optimization

Adjustments were made to the simulation model as part of this study. The entire simulation and optimization model used in this study can be found in Eloranta (2023b). These adjustments were implemented to better align the model with the characteristics of the biogas production from agricultural waste and side-flows. In contrast to the initial model developed by Niemitalo & Ekkerman (2022), which assumed consistent factors influencing the dynamics of waste collection and transportation, the model used in this study was further developed to account for various types of biomasses being collected and transported.

This development was necessary due to the distinct requirements for collecting grasses and straws, dry and slurry manure, each of which necessitates different types of vehicles and results in differing collection rates. Henceforth, within this study, the terms "grass and straw," "dry manure", and "slurry manure" will collectively refer to the three general types of biomasses. In the study's model, it was assumed that grass and straw bales are collected and transported as piece goods, secured with straps during transportation. Collecting slurry manure involves specialized intake equipment integrated into a container on the transportation vehicle, while dry manures are gathered in a closed boxcar. Overall, the study's model was expanded to encompass different types of biomasses for collection and transportation. This expansion built upon the initial model introduced by Niemitalo & Ekkerman (2022) to ensure the validity and realism of simulating the biogas supply chain.

General assumptions regarding the logistic simulation and routing optimization were made as follows: a total of 9 collection trucks were assumed, with an equal distribution among general biomass types. The simulation calculates the instances of wrong visits for each vehicle and applies penalties during the optimization process to ensure logical routes for each vehicle. An example of an incorrect visit occurs when a vehicle, originally intended to collect dry manure, visits a pickup site containing grass or straw and attempts, unsuccessfully, to collect biomass from within that site. The capacity of each truck was assumed to be 45 tons. The duration of the work shift was set to 9 hours, including a break of 45 minutes. Since the targeted input values for biomasses were set on an annual level (Tampio, 2023), the length of the simulation period was set to be one year, representing 251 workdays. Number of depot sites were set to one, including the coordinates of the biogas plant under construction.

During the simulation, additional adjustments were made due to the presence of three types of biomasses. The depot site, designed to mimic the biogas plant, was expanded

to incorporate storage capacities for the various biomass types and to monitor their levels. For manures, the storage capacity was set at 14,000 tons, while for grasses and straws, it was set at 28,000 tons. These capacities aligned with the targeted input values for biomasses established by the case company (Tampio, 2023).

In relation to manures, the capacity of pickup sites was defined as the sum of masses within the clusters. This definition adheres to regulations requiring farms to be capable of storing the amount of manure produced annually (Government Decree on the Restriction of Discharge of Nitrates From Agriculture into Waters 2000/931 § 4). Notably, the clustering datasets are based on an annual timeframe. For grasses and straws, a theoretical capacity was similarly set, although its impact on optimization was disregarded, as grasses and straws are assumed to be stored as bales in fields, essentially having infinite capacity.

Cluster centroids were modeled as pickup site locations, serving as collection points for the biomasses within the designated area of each cluster. For simulation purposes, initial storage levels of the pickup sites were selected randomly to prevent potential systematic errors that could result from uniform or constant level settings. These initial levels were determined for manure pickup sites by multiplying the site's capacity by a random number between 0 and 0.8. Regarding grass and straw pickup sites, 40% of the pickup sites were randomly selected to include a storage level that represents the amount of collectable grass and straw generated from a single cutting. This level corresponds to a third of the annual accumulation of grass and straws, considering that three cuttings occur within a year.

Different dynamics within the accumulation and collection processes of various generic biomass types at the pickup sites were taken into consideration. These dynamics were subsequently implemented into the simulation model. The accumulation of manures was assumed to follow a linear pattern, based on discussions with experts from HAMK and LuKe, where it was concluded to be a reasonable assumption. The fulfillment process of the pickup sites within the manure sites were thus modeled as follows:

$$\Delta m_{t,i} = m_i, \quad (1)$$

where $\Delta m_{t,i}$ is an accumulation of manure at the day t on the pickup site i , m_i is a daily expected accumulation of manure at the site i , derived by dividing the site's annual accumulation with the length of the simulation period.

Assuming a similar linear accumulation process with the grasses and straws would be inappropriate due to the need for cutting before collection, which only takes place during the summer. Consequently, an alternative accumulation process became necessary. It

was assumed that farms perform three cuttings during the summer: the first in mid-June, the second at the beginning of August, and the third in mid-September. Once these cuts are completed, the storage level at a pickup site goes from zero to one-third of the annual production for that site. To prevent simultaneous jumps at all sites, the jumps were distributed over three two-week periods: mid-June, the beginning of August, and mid-September. Each site was allowed a jump only once during a two-week period, resulting in a maximum of three jumps per site throughout the simulation period.

During a two-week period, the accumulation process was modeled as follows:

$$\Delta m_{t,i} = \frac{1}{3} M_i \varepsilon_{t,i}, \quad (2)$$

in which $\Delta m_{t,i}$ is the accumulation of grass or straw at the day t on the pickup site i , M_i is the annual accumulation of grass or straw at site i , and ε is a vector consisting of 10 elements, with 9 of them being zeros and one element equal to 1. The location of this element within the vector, i.e., the date of the jump occurrence, was chosen randomly. The accumulation of grasses and straws follows Equation 2 only if the simulation is in one of the three two-week periods during which the cuttings are expected to occur. Otherwise, the accumulation of grasses and straws is zero.

It should be noted that each site had a unique ε for each two-week period, ensuring that the cuttings did not occur on the exact same day for every site within that period, thus increasing the randomness of the simulation. Additionally, ε was initially generated for routing optimization and remained fixed for the optimization process. The decision to fix ε values was made because optimizing the routing would not yield actual optimality if ε values were completely random. This is because the optimization problem would change with each simulation run during the optimization process.

To address the third research question, additional time-sensitive factors that influence the levels of biomass volume and moisture were incorporated into the model. The effect of passive drying of biomass was modeled, utilizing the storage model presented by van Dyken et al. (2010). The passive drying dynamics were applied to all simulation schemes.

The rate of biomass volume loss due to passive drying is assumed to be 1% per week within the storage model of van Dyken et al. (2010). Therefore, the time-critical factor representing the volume losses of biomasses caused by passive drying was modeled as follows:

$$V_{b,w} = V_b (1 - r_{l,d})^w, \quad (3)$$

where $V_{b,w}$ is the volume of biomass b at week w , V_b is the initial volume level of biomass at the location of interest, and $r_{l,d}$ is the rate of biomass volume loss caused by passive drying on a weekly basis.

Due to passive drying, the moisture level of biomasses decreases, affecting their TS-rate. The decreasing drying rate of biomasses was defined in timestep within the storage model of van Dyken et al. (2010). However, due to the broader complexity of this study's problem, including the accumulation and consumption of biomasses, the modeling of changes within the biomasses' level of moisture was simplified and not defined by timestep. In this study, a 5% decrease in moisture content per week through passive drying was assumed, based on the approximation of van Dyken et al.'s (2010) drying rate, which is dependent on storage time. Therefore, the time-critical factor representing the changes in the moisture level, later being transformed to changes within the TS rate, was modeled as follows:

$$M_{b,w} = M_b(1 - r_{m,d})^w, \quad (4)$$

where $M_{b,w}$ is the level of moisture of biomass b at week w , M_b is the initial level of moisture of biomass at the location of interest, and $r_{m,d}$ is the rate of biomass moisture decrease caused by passive drying on a weekly basis. The dynamics of passive drying, as presented in Equations 3 and 4, were assumed to be valid at storages of pickup sites, during transportation, and at the storage of the biogas plant before being utilized within the AD process.

The assumption of a constant pickup duration (Niemitalo & Ekkerman, 2022) was rejected within this study. This rejection may be justified by the coexistence of multiple types of biomasses and the dependence of pickup duration on the amount of biomass to be picked up. It was assumed that the pickup duration consists of a constant factor and a variable that is linearly dependent on the amount of biomass to be collected. The pickup duration may be formatted as follows:

$$\Delta t_{i,l} = T + v_m l, \quad (5)$$

where $\Delta t_{i,l}$ is the pickup duration for the pickup site i with a load level of l , T is the constant term of the pickup operation, and v_m is the collection rate for the biomass m . T was assumed to be 10 minutes for all biomasses, based on the discussions had with the experts of HAMK and LuKe. Therefore, T may be considered as the setting time of a pickup operation, including the time spent on setting up and dismantling the collection equipment. Based on the discussions with the experts, v_m was assumed to be 1.6 tons/min \Leftrightarrow 0.625 min/ton for slurry manures, 1 ton/min \Leftrightarrow 1 min/ton for dry manures,

and 1.2 ton/min \Leftrightarrow 0.833 min/ton for grasses and straws. Although grasses and straws accumulate only in summer, it was assumed that once the cuttings are done, they are baled and stored in the fields, allowing the collection of them to be continuous throughout the year. It should be noted that the vehicle may not be able to empty the site if its load reaches its capacity. In that case, the vehicle loads only the amount it's able to, and the time spent on that operation is calculated based on the loaded level.

To facilitate monitoring the storage levels of general biomass types within the biogas plant and to analyze the fulfillment of TS-rate requirements within the wet process used in the biogas production (Hadin & Eriksson, 2016), the implementation of the depot class (Niemitalo & Ekkerman, 2022) was significantly expanded. The biogas plant is modeled as an object constructed by the depot class in the simulation. Methods for receiving biomass into storage and consuming it from storage were implemented, along with methods to track and update storage levels within the biogas plant and its TS rate. The necessary object variables were also defined (Eloranta, 2023b). These variables include the storage levels of the biogas plant, cumulative amounts of received biomasses, weighted average of the TS rate within the storage, cumulative dilution water consumed, and consumption rates. The consumption rates were defined through discussions with experts from LuKe and HAMK Bio, replicating the potential mixture utilization within the biogas reactor.

In the simulation, the storage levels of biomasses decrease each day by the consumption rates, which represent the utilization of resources in the biogas production. When a vehicle arrives at the biogas plant to unload, the plant's biomass-receiving method is invoked. This action increases storage levels by the amount unloaded by the vehicle and updates the weighted average of the TS rate of the storage. The logging of storage levels and TS rate has been implemented to facilitate post-analysis for assessing the fulfillment of the 15% TS rate requirement.

Additional object variables were introduced for the depot class to enable the identification of unfavorable actions within the biogas production process, similar to the cost variables in the optimizer's cost function discussed in more detail in the following subchapter 3.5.2. A cumulative amount of received biomass was implemented to track the moment when the received quantity of biomass reaches the yearly targeted input value. If this occurs, subsequent unloads executed by vehicles are unnecessary and are counted and penalized within the cost function. Overfilling of the biogas plant's storage is also considered as a cost variable within the cost function and is penalized on a daily basis. If the storage level of the biogas plant reaches zero, it causes a production stoppage, which is also penalized within the cost function based on the number of days with biogas production

stopped. To maximize the likelihood of generating an optimized routing with a continuously maintained TS rate below 15% within the storage, the cumulative consumption of dilution water in the biogas production has been introduced. Each day, if the storage's TS rate exceeds 15%, the total consumption of dilution water increases by the amount required to dilute the storage's biomass mixture to achieve a TS rate of 15%. The cumulative consumption of dilution water is incorporated as a single cost term within the cost function minimized by the GA, a topic that will be discussed in the next subsection.

3.5.2 Genetic algorithm in optimization

A genetic algorithm (GA) implemented by Niemitalo & Ekkerman (2022) is utilized as part of this study to optimize the collection and logistic routing of biomasses in a way that minimizes the cost function to be defined. GAs are population-based metaheuristics approaches to solve optimization problems, suitable for variety of problems in the field of operations management (Katoch et al. 2021). During the optimization process of population-based metaheuristics, multiple potential solutions are simultaneously maintained, evaluated, compared, and evolved. The diversity is maintained in the population to avoid the solutions from being stuck in local optimum. The principles that guide the optimization of the genetic algorithm are derived from the biological evolution process. (Katoch et al. 2021) In short, GA's optimization starts with a set of solutions, noted as the initial population. A single solution within the population is noted as a chromosome. By utilizing a set of genetic operators, new potential solutions, noted as children, are generated by combining the parts, noted as genes, of the initial solutions, noted as parents. The feasibility of a solution is examined with the defined fitness function. Based on the value of the fitness function, a solution is either accepted to the population or rejected. If the solution is accepted, a new generation of solutions is established. The process of inheriting potential solutions is repeated until the defined stopping criteria are met. (Gracia et al. 2014)

The implementation of the GA includes a set of discrete phases. These phases encompass setting the parameters, the initialization of the population, i.e. selecting the initial parents, defining the fitness value, i.e. cost function based on the conditions and goals of the optimization context, defining the crossover and mutation operators utilized to inherit new solutions, and the replacement of each generation. (Gracia et al. 2014) The crossover and mutation operators are referred to as genetic operators, implemented not only to inherit descendants, i.e. generate new solutions, but also to maintain the diversity of the population and avoid ending up with a solution located in a local optimum (Gracia et al. 2014; Katoch et al. 2021).

The implementation of the GA utilized in this study is as follows. The parameters such as the population size, number of genes, and generations (Gracia et al. 2014) are set as follows: the number of genes, i.e. the number of potential locations to be visited by a vehicle (including pickup sites and the biogas plant), is calculated from the simulated logistic routing proposal. The size of the population is derived as follows:

$$S_p = \max(100, 4N_g), \quad (6)$$

where S_p is the size of the population used within the optimization, and N_g is the number of genes calculated from the routing information. Based on the routing input information given to the algorithm, size of population within this study was calculated to be 12,384. The number of generations to be inherited serves as the stopping criteria for the optimization and was set to 600,000. After 400,000 generations were completed, the algorithm switched to a greedy approach for the remaining 200,000 generations, utilizing a greedy optimization algorithm. The difference between the non-greedy and greedy algorithms will be explained in the next paragraph. The initial population is generated randomly. For each initial solution, a random permutation of integers is generated from 0 to $N_g - 1$, in which each integer represents one gene in the chromosome.

Before inheriting descendants, i.e., utilizing the crossover operator, a selection of chromosomes from which the new solutions are generated is done. Selection is a crucial step in optimization if the GA is utilized since it determines which portion of the initial solutions will be included in the optimization process, and later on, the selection is applied with inherited generations. (Katoch et al. 2021) The selection procedure implemented by Niemitalo and Ekkerman (2022) and utilized within this study does not narrow the number of chromosomes while inheriting new generations of solutions. It takes each chromosome as a parent p_0 and chooses another chromosome randomly as a parent p_1 , with each chromosome being chosen randomly only once. Therefore, each chromosome within the generation is utilized once as a parent p_0 and once as a parent p_1 . However, after switching to a greedy approach, the algorithm fixes the choice of the other parent to be the best-known chromosome, i.e., the best among the simulated solutions thus far. (Niemitalo & Ekkerman, 2022) Consequently, the number of potential descendants equals the number of parents. By not narrowing the number of descendants within the inherited generations, the chances of ending up with a solution located in a local optimum are decreased since the best chromosome is chosen at the end of the optimization with the best fitness value, i.e., the lowest cost.

The creation of descendants is done by the crossover operator after the selection procedure. The crossover operator determines the combination of genes for descendants,

consisting of parts of the parents' genes. (Gracia et al. 2014; Katoch et al. 2021) The crossover operator implemented by Niemitalo and Ekkerman (2022) and utilized within this study chooses two random crossover points from the chromosome of parent p_1 and transmits the genes between the crossover points to the child. The rest of the genes are transmitted to the child from parent p_0 , from which the genes that are not in between the previously chosen crossover points are chosen. Thus, a new descendant is generated with genes consisting of parts of its parents' genes.

Mutation operators could be implemented to add random variations to the genes of children with determined probabilities (Gracia et al. 2014). However, mutation operators were not implemented in the GA utilized within this study (Niemitalo & Ekkerman, 2022). Mutation operators would maintain the diversity within the population across the generations, ensuring the avoidance of ending up in a local optimum (Katoch et al. 2021). However, since the number of chromosomes within generations is not narrowed through the inheritance process, the implementation of a separate mutation operator was not seen as a necessity for this study.

After inheriting descendants, the feasibility of each chromosome is evaluated using the cost function. The value of the cost function with the inherited chromosome is calculated and compared to the cost function values of its parents. The chromosome with the lowest cost function value is accepted into the new generation of solutions. (Niemitalo & Ekkerman, 2022) Therefore, it is ensured that each round of generations improves or maintains a set of solutions equally good as the previous generation by rejecting the child from the inherited generation if its cost is higher than either of its parents.

The cost function utilized within this study is based on the one implemented by Niemitalo and Ekkerman (2022) and has been further developed for this study to better align its functioning with the context of transporting agricultural wastes and side-flows as biomasses for utilization in the biogas production. The cost function utilized within the optimization of this study is defined as follows:

$$TC = c_{ovld} \sum_{i=1}^m OVLD_i + C_{vehicles} + C_{bgp}, \quad (7)$$

where TC is the total costs caused by the system with the given routing, c_{ovld} is the assumed cost of one day of overload at a pickup site, $OVLD_i$ is the number of days of overloading at pickup site i and m is the number of pickup sites.

$C_{vehicles}$ consist of costs caused by vehicles, and is defined as follows:

$$C_{\text{vehicles}} = p_f c_f \sum_{i=1}^n \text{ODO}_i + c_{\text{ovth}} \sum_{i=1}^n \text{OVT}_i + c_{\text{wv}} \sum_{i=1}^n \text{WV}_i, \quad (8)$$

where p_f is the assumed price of fuel (€/l), c_f is the assumed fuel consumption (l/100km), n is the number of vehicles collecting and transporting the biomasses from farms to the biogas plant, ODO_i is the total mileage driven by vehicle i with the given routing, c_{ovth} is the assumed cost of the overtime work (€/h), OVT_i is the total overtime work of vehicle i with the given routing, c_{wv} represents the unit cost for a vehicle visiting the wrong type of pickup site, and WV_i signifies the number of wrong visits carried out by vehicle i based on the given routing. The incorporation of cost terms penalizing wrong visits was a component of the ongoing development of the cost function, which was undertaken as part of this study. Other cost terms associated with vehicles were introduced by Niemitalo & Ekkerman (2022), along with the cost term for pickup site overload, as presented in Equation 7.

C_{bgp} was a part of further development of the cost function implemented by Niemitalo and Ekkerman (2022), and it represents costs caused by inefficiencies in biogas production at the biogas plant. C_{bgp} is defined as follows:

$$C_{\text{bgp}} = c_{\text{pdst}} \text{PDST} + c_{\text{ovf}} \text{OVF} + c_{\text{exim}} \text{EXIM} + c_{\text{dw}} \text{DW}, \quad (9)$$

where c_{pdst} is the assumed cost of a production stoppage, i.e. biogas plant running out of feedstock storage, PDST is the number of production stoppages that occurred within the simulation with the given routing, c_{ovf} is the assumed cost of overfilling the biogas plant's storage, which is assumed to have a capacity equal to the targeted annual inputs (Tampio, 2023), OVF is the number of overstocking occurrences that happened with the given routing, c_{exim} is the assumed cost of one unnecessary import of biomasses to the biogas plant after the targeted annual input is reached, EXIM represents the number of unnecessary imports that occurred within the simulation with the given routing, c_{dw} represents the assumed cost for one ton of dilution water consumed, and DW signifies the total amount of dilution water, in tons, consumed at the biogas plant based on the given routing.

It should be noted that Equations 7, 8 and 9 all include penalty terms that are difficult to measure, but practical and reasonable to utilize within optimization procedure to ensure the streamlining of the related phases in the biogas supply chain. These penalty terms are costs of overloading of pickup sites, costs of wrong visits, costs of production stoppages and overfills of the feedstock storage at the biogas plant, and costs of unnecessary imports of biomasses.

Although Equation 7 shows the general cost term for overloads at pickup sites, it should be noted that overfilling of grass and straw pickup sites was neglected within the optimization. Since it was assumed that grasses and straws are baled on the fields, a theoretical infinite storage capacity could be assumed. Therefore, the cost function term $OVLD_i$'s value was not increased during the simulation if storage level exceeded site's capacity at pickup site consisting of grass or straw, resulting in neglect of overloads at grass or straw pickup sites.

The cost function presented in the Equation 7 was utilized in this study because it considers the dynamic optimization of logistic routing, aims to minimize transportation costs (mileage and overtime work), and consequently, aims to reduce transportation emissions (by minimizing mileage and fuel consumption). It also aims to enhance the flow of biomasses within the biogas supply chain by taking into account biomass flows at the biogas plant and addressing potential inefficiencies that might arise, including the consumption of dilution water and occurrences of production stoppages. These factors are consistent with those presented in Figure 5 of Chapter 2.6, which illustrates the factors within the biogas supply chain that can be improved using the methods developed and utilized in this study. The methods also consider case-specific factors related to the CBE and the transportation of agricultural wastes and side-flows as biomasses to be utilized in the biogas production, based on the literature review presented and discussed in Chapter 2.

3.6 Validity and reliability of the methodology

Throughout the research process, ensuring high-quality standards was of utmost importance. This involved acknowledging the factors that influence the validity and reliability of the research and considering their potential threats. Validity is concerned with the accuracy and integrity of the research process, ensuring that it effectively addresses the intended subjects and problems through appropriate data collection and analysis methods, leading to credible and dependable results (Saunders et al. 2019). The examination of validity involves assessing whether the utilized methodologies effectively measure the intended variables and phenomena. Moreover, it includes evaluating the soundness of the analysis of results and the conclusions drawn from them. Additionally, the generalizability of the study's findings and methodologies to a broader context should be examined. The content of the study should also be validated, with the correct and accurate application of terms related to the research subject. Furthermore, it should be considered whether the utilized methods sufficiently cover the phenomenon under study. Ultimately, the goal is to have results that can be explained based on the utilized variables rather than the research process itself. (Saunders et al. 2019)

The methodology successfully covered the intended topics. The dynamics of CBE and the collection and transportation of agricultural wastes and side-flows as biomasses were analyzed comprehensively in Chapter 2's literature review. Insights derived from this review were then considered in later simulation schemes and optimization procedures, ensuring alignment of the upcoming results with the case-specific conditions and requirements. Ultimately, the key insights from the literature review are presented in Figure 5. By comparing it with the data processing methodologies in Chapter 3.4 used to locate biomass potentials within the relevant area, as well as the simulation schemes and GA's cost function in chapters 3.5, 3.5.1, and 3.5.2, all with case-specific adjustments, it can be argued that this study successfully aimed to measure and improve the aspects presented in Figure 5.

However, it should be noted that this study has its restrictions regarding the quality of the initial geospatial data processed to model the pickup sites via clustering, as well as regarding the generalizability of the methods and the results, caused by implemented and assumed case-specific adjustments. The limitations of the study are discussed in more detail in Chapter 6.2.

The replication and consistency of the study are referred to as reliability (Saunders et al. 2019). Due to the utilization of publicly available geospatial datasets for biomasses (LuKe, 2023), the development and utilization of quantitative methods for data processing with open-source code (Eloranta, 2023a), and the simulation approach to optimization utilizing a GA with open-source code (Niemitalo & Ekkerman, 2022; Eloranta, 2023b), replication of the study can be argued to be high. To replicate the study, one should possess basic knowledge of installing Python and C++ and related packages and running source code files utilizing those with the integrated development environment of their choice.

Consistency of the study can also be argued to be high since the research process is described comprehensively and transparently step by step within this study. It starts with the literature review in Chapter 2 and forms the theoretical framework presented in Figure 5. It then continues by describing the optimization problem at a conceptual level and the data processing phases in detail in Chapters 3.2, 3.3, and 3.4, concluding with the model development by presenting the simulation approach and the GA to be utilized within the optimization in Chapters 3.5, 3.5.1, and 3.5.2.

4 RESULTS

This chapter reports the results of the study. Initially, the results addressing the second and third research questions are presented in subsections 4.1 and 4.2. These results include the performance indicator values of the biogas supply chain, for which logistic routing was optimized. As the results are related to logistic routing planning on an annual basis, this chapter presents the selected performance indicators of the system produced with optimized routings. Comprehensive routing plans are excluded from the study as they exist in the form of raw data, including routes for nine vehicles each day within a year. The chapter closes by benchmarking the results with randomized and practical base case routings.

4.1 Optimized routing

The optimized routing for collecting and transporting biomasses from sites to the biogas plant, without assuming the time-criticality of biomass, was addressed first, in response to the second research question. This optimized routing plan covers nine vehicles designated for collecting biomasses from sites, with an equal distribution among various biomass types. In other words, every third vehicle is assigned to collect grasses and straws, among others. The routing was optimized and presented using location indexes, which are employed in simulation and optimization, with each index representing a site generated within Chapter 3.4 or the biogas plant.

The optimization trajectory is shown in Figure 16. This trajectory represents the lowest cost within the population of routing proposals, as a function of the number of cost function evaluations (Niemitalo & Ekkerman, 2022). The number of cost function evaluations increases by the population size of 12,384 within each generation during the optimization process. The number of generations was set to 600,000, serving as a stopping criterion for optimization. The switch to the greedy optimization algorithm can be observed in Figure 16 after 400,000 generations, resulting in an acceleration of the total cost minimization, which corresponds to 4,953,600 thousand cost function calculations.

Figure 16. Routing optimization progress.

The performance of the optimized routing was assessed by calculating the values of performance indicators using the optimized routing. These performance indicators correspond to the cost terms included within the cost function presented in Equations 7, 8, and 9 in Chapter 3.5.2, which were minimized during the routing optimization process. The values of the performance indicators are presented below in Tables 1 and 2. Table 1 covers vehicle-specific performance indicators, while Table 2 covers the performance indicators of the biogas plant, and the vehicles as a whole.

Upon analyzing and comparing Figure 16 with Tables 1 and 2, it can be concluded that the optimized routing plan is a viable solution for the BRBPP problem in this case. However, it may not be the ultimate optimal solution to the problem.

Continuous biomass flow is ensured with the optimized routing at the biogas plant, as evidenced by zero production stoppages in the biogas production. Concerning overtime work, the optimized routing meets the objective of not extending any routes beyond working hours, as the overtime for each vehicle is zero hours.

Still, the mileage of vehicles could probably be further minimized if the number of wrong visits were optimized to be zero for each vehicle. Wrong visits occur within the optimized routing, indicating that vehicles are driving unnecessary extra kilometers. This means that the optimized routing plan includes routes for vehicles that involve visiting the wrong types of pickup sites.

In the globally optimal solution, each vehicle should make zero wrong visits, meaning they only visit the designated pickup sites. Another factor supporting the suboptimality of the solution is the fact that the slope curve of the total costs in Figure 16 still seems to be negative at the end of the optimization, indicating the possible existence of solutions producing lower total costs.

The optimized routing can be further improved by filtering out wrong visits from the routes. Since each vehicle and pickup site has an attribute called type, sites that don't match a vehicle's type from the routing can be excluded. After this filtering process, new performance indicators can be calculated by rerunning the simulation using the optimized and filtered routing. The performance indicators of the filtered routing are compared to the indicator values provided with the optimized routing below in Tables 1 and 2.

Table 1. The vehicle-specific performance indicators.

	<i>Type of the vehicle</i>	<i>Mileage (km)</i>	<i>Wrong visits</i>	<i>Overtime (h)</i>	<i>Mileage with the filtered routing (km)</i>
Vehicle 1	Slurry manure	2,419.09	47	0	276.59
Vehicle 2	Grass/straw	1,204.33	18	0	564.67
Vehicle 3	Dry manure	4,436.51	32	0	3,219.76
Vehicle 4	Slurry manure	2,375.23	57	0	148.63
Vehicle 5	Dry manure	4,009.24	22	0	2,997.21
Vehicle 6	Grass/straw	1,335.37	16	0	662.39
Vehicle 7	Slurry manure	3,070.02	62	0	288.79
Vehicle 8	Grass/straw	1,640.47	18	0	901.84
Vehicle 9	Dry manure	6,643.38	41	0	4,367.31

Table 2. The performance indicators of the biogas plant and vehicles.

	<i>Optimized routing</i>	<i>Optimized and filtered routing</i>
Total mileage (km)	27,133.63	13,427.20
Total wrong visits	313	0
Total overtime (h)	0	0
Number of days with no routes	29	74
Total pickup site overload days	11,062	11,062
Production stoppages	0	0
Consumption of dilution water (tons)	998,452	998,452
Unnecessary imports to the biogas plant	0	0
Overfillings within the biogas plant	0	0
Total costs (€)	5,858,387.13	5,545,373.43

However, although the performance of the optimized routing can be improved by filtering out wrong visits from the optimized routing, as demonstrated in Tables 1 and 2, it should be noted that the results provided by the optimized and filtered routing should not be considered as the global optimum solution.

Since the consumption of dilution water almost reaches a million tons with the optimized and filtered routing, it suggests the possible existence of solutions with lower total costs. In principle, if there are biomass inputs, i.e., pickup sites, with a TS content lower than 15%, it should be possible to find solutions that require no dilution water consumption at all by limiting the routing to sites with a TS lower than 15%. As indicated by the biomass datasets (LuKe, 2023) used for site clustering in Chapter 3.4, slurry manure has TS rates of 8.2% and 9.2%. However, if optimization were constrained to include only visits to slurry manure sites, the impact on other cost factors within the simulation remains unclear. This constraint could potentially improve the solution in terms of dilution water

consumption but weaken it in terms of other cost factors, potentially moving it further away from the global optimum.

4.2 Optimized routing under the assumption of biomass time-criticality

The optimized routing for collecting and transporting biomasses from sites to the biogas plant, considering the time-criticality of biomasses as described in Equations 3 and 4 in Chapter 3.5.1, was addressed as the second aspect in response to the third research question. This routing plan was optimized and presented in a unified format, in contrast to the routing plan found in Chapter 4.1, which covers nine vehicles of three types distributed equally. The routing uses similar location indexes, and the routes were optimized on a daily basis for all vehicles.

The optimization trajectory is presented in Figure 17. The optimization process shared fundamental similarities with that of Figure 16. In both cases, a similar cost function, as described in Equation 7 in Chapter 3.5.2, was utilized. Figure 17's trajectory similarly depicts the lowest cost within the population of routing proposals as a function of the number of cost function evaluations (Niemitalo & Ekkerman, 2022). The optimization process involved a population size of 12,384, and the stopping criteria for optimization were set at 600,000 generations. A switch to the greedy optimization algorithm occurred after 400,000 generations, as can be observed in Figure 17's trajectory, after 4,953,600 thousand cost function calculations, where the minimization of total costs begins to accelerate.

Figure 17. Routing optimization progress under the assumption of biomass time-criticality.

Similar performance indicators, as found in Tables 1 and 2 in Chapter 4.1, were calculated to assess the performance of the optimized routing under the assumption of biomass time-criticality as well. These indicators are specific to both vehicles and the system, corresponding to cost terms within the simulation model and its cost function that was optimized using the GA. They are presented below in Tables 3 and 4, with Table 3 focusing on vehicle-specific indicators and Table 4 on system-specific indicators, covering all vehicles and the biogas plant.

Based on the analysis and comparison of Figure 17 and Tables 3 and 4, similar conclusions can be drawn about the performance of the optimized routing when considering the time-criticality of biomass, as discussed in Chapter 4.1 for the routing that was optimized without the time-criticality assumption. While the optimized routing is a viable solution for the BRBPP with the inclusion of time-critical biomass, it must be noted that it may not be the ultimate optimal solution to the problem.

The suboptimality of the solution can be observed through the number of wrong visits that occurred within the simulation using the optimized routing in Tables 3 and 4. The number of wrong visits should be zero in the global optimal solution since wrong visits imply unnecessary and additional kilometers driven by vehicles during the simulation. Similarly, as seen in the optimization presented in Chapter 4.1, the total costs still appear to decrease at the end of the optimization in Figure 17, with the slope curve of the total costs showing a negative trend. This suggests the possible existence of solutions that could produce lower total costs.

Similarly to Chapter 4.1, the optimized routing can be further improved by filtering out wrong visits from the routing. The performance indicators under the assumption of biomass time-criticality, along with the optimized and filtered routing, are compared to the optimized results within Tables 3 and 4.

Table 3. The vehicle-specific performance indicators under the assumption of biomass time-criticality.

	<i>Type of the vehicle</i>	<i>Mileage (km)</i>	<i>Wrong visits</i>	<i>Overtime (h)</i>	<i>Mileage with the filtered routing (km)</i>
Vehicle 1	Slurry manure	927.42	14	0	329.45
Vehicle 2	Grass/straw	352.08	7	0	65.01
Vehicle 3	Dry manure	3,568.97	17	0	2,774.14
Vehicle 4	Slurry manure	1,124.62	14	0	235.92
Vehicle 5	Dry manure	4,599.48	10	0	4,132.51
Vehicle 6	Grass/straw	352.00	4	0	182.47
Vehicle 7	Slurry manure	559.80	14	0	148.62
Vehicle 8	Grass/straw	230.10	6	0	58.44
Vehicle 9	Dry manure	3,621.91	8	0	3,270.08

Table 4. The performance indicators of the biogas plant and vehicles under the assumption of biomass time-criticality.

	<i>Optimized routing</i>	<i>Optimized and filtered routing</i>
Total mileage (km)	15,336.4	11,196.65
Total wrong visits	94	0
Total overtime (h)	0	0
Number of days with no routes	74	95
Total pickup site overload days	10,666	10,666
Production stoppages	0	0
Consumption of dilution water (tons)	950,863	950,863
Unnecessary imports to the biogas plant	0	0
Overfillings within the biogas plant	0	0
Total costs (€)	5,381,630.34	5,287,626.20

Filtering out wrong visits improves the solution in terms of total costs, mileage, and the number of wrong visits. However, the results of the filtered routing should not be considered as the global optimum, as there are likely solutions with lower total costs. This is indicated by the high consumption of dilution water and the number of pickup site overload days in Table 4.

Still, the goodness of the solution can be argued again with the number of production stoppages, total overtime hours of zero, and unnecessary imports to the biogas plant being zero. This implicates that with the given routing, continuous biomass flow and bi-

ogas production process was ensured within the biogas plant, simultaneously not exceeding the yearly targeted input values for biomasses at the biogas plant and not including routes exceeding the work shifts.

4.3 Benchmarking of results

The results for both cases, as presented in Chapters 4.1 and 4.2, were validated and benchmarked by comparing the performance of optimized routings to randomized routings and routings that correspond to a practical approach to biomass routing, serving as a base case in benchmarking. In the randomized routing, the vehicle routing is chaotic. In the baseline routing, controlled collection of biomasses in response to orders arising randomly at the farms is assumed. These benchmarks were based on calculating performance indicator values, similar to the approach used in Chapters 4.1 and 4.2 with optimized routings.

The benchmark routings used in these comparisons were generated by utilizing the same simulation and optimization model as presented in Chapters 3.5, 3.5.1, and 3.5.2. However, the number of generations to be optimized was set at 100, serving as a stopping criterion for the optimization process. Since the initial population is generated randomly by the GA (Gracia et al. 2014; Katoch et al. 2021), the solution obtained by stopping the optimization after 100 generations is also close to a random solution and is used as the randomized routing in benchmarks.

Filtering out wrong visits from the randomized routing can be intuitively considered as the baseline solution for routing the collection of biomasses used in biogas production. In this scenario, orders for collecting biomasses from farms are generated randomly. Biomass pickup trucks are used to collect and transport the biomasses back to the biogas plant based on the orders. If there are multiple orders for the same truck on the same day, the truck collects them all within its capacity limits before returning to the biogas plant. Hence, the baseline routing can be considered a practical solution used by real-world logistical operators who collect biomasses in an order-controlled manner.

4.3.1 Benchmarks of the optimized routing

Benchmarks for the optimized routing results presented in the Chapter 4.1, are shown below in Tables 5 and 6. Tables covers the performance indicators of the randomized and the baseline routing.

Table 5. The vehicle-specific performance indicators with the randomized routing (1) and baseline routing (2).

	<i>Type of the vehicle</i>	<i>Mileage (1) (km)</i>	<i>Wrong visits (1)</i>	<i>Overtime (1) (h)</i>	<i>Mileage (2) (km)</i>	<i>Overtime (2) (h)</i>
Vehicle 1	Slurry manure	3,841.94	76	0	74.26	0
Vehicle 2	Grass/straw	4,782.23	58	0	2,472.88	0
Vehicle 3	Dry manure	4,639.28	61	0	2,063.67	0
Vehicle 4	Slurry manure	4,210.87	85	0	15.56	0
Vehicle 5	Dry manure	4,796.84	62	0	1,833.60	0
Vehicle 6	Grass/straw	3,991.96	64	0	1,532.51	0
Vehicle 7	Slurry manure	4,732.29	96	0	77.98	0
Vehicle 8	Grass/straw	3,508.54	44	0	1,495.74	0
Vehicle 9	Dry manure	4,186.06	49	0	1,658.06	0

Table 6. The performance indicators of the biogas plant and vehicles with the randomized routing and baseline routing.

	<i>Randomized routing</i>	<i>Baseline routing</i>
Total mileage (km)	38,690.02	11,224.26
Total wrong visits	595	0
Total overtime (h)	0	0
Number of days with no routes	16	101
Total pickup site overload days	13,684	13,684
Production stoppages	53	53
Consumption of dilution water (tons)	7,252,490	7,252,490
Unnecessary imports to the biogas plant	0	0
Overfillings within the biogas plant	0	0
Total costs (€)	42,841,688.69	42,246,661.22

By comparing the performance of the optimized routings, as presented in Tables 1 and 2 in Chapter 4.1, with the performance of randomized and base case routings, as presented in Tables 5 and 6 above, the appropriateness of the developed simulation model and optimization method can be justified. In comparison to the practical baseline approach to biomass routing, where the collection of biomasses is triggered only by orders arising from the farms, a high number of production stoppages may occur within a year, as the baseline routing does not consider resource needs and production stoppages as a factor to be considered in routing. Such significant addition in the number of production

stoppages greatly contributes to the total costs of the system. Randomized routing generates even greater total costs since a high number of additional kilometers are driven by vehicles due to wrong visits.

4.3.2 Benchmarks of the optimized routing under the assumption of biomass time-criticality

Benchmarks for the results that considered the time-criticality of biomass, as presented in Chapter 4.2, are shown below in Tables 7 and 8. Tables benchmarks the performance of the optimized results with the performances of the randomized and the baseline routing.

Table 7. The vehicle-specific performance indicators with the randomized routing (1) and baseline routing (2) under the assumption of biomass time-criticality.

	Type of the vehicle	Mileage (1) (km)	Wrong visits (1)	Overtime (1) (h)	Mileage (2) (km)	Overtime (2) (h)
Vehicle 1	Slurry manure	4,103.60	86	0	123.99	0
Vehicle 2	Grass/straw	3,394.59	36	0	1,920.22	0
Vehicle 3	Dry manure	4,149.73	48	0	2,321.36	0
Vehicle 4	Slurry manure	3,583.74	75	0	59.69	0
Vehicle 5	Dry manure	4,486.19	44	0	2,371.47	0
Vehicle 6	Grass/straw	3,781.46	42	0	1,943.40	0
Vehicle 7	Slurry manure	4,688.62	99	0	124.90	0
Vehicle 8	Grass/straw	5,743.46	61	0	3,216.70	0
Vehicle 9	Dry manure	4,270.88	54	0	1,570.06	0

Table 8. The performance indicators of the biogas plant and vehicles with the randomized routing and baseline routing.

	Randomized routing	Baseline routing
Total mileage (km)	38,202.26	13,651.79
Total wrong visits	545	0
Total overtime (h)	0	0
Number of days with no routes	14	88
Total pickup site overload days	13,018	13,018
Production stoppages	34	34
Consumption of dilution water (tons)	7,995,460	7,995,460
Unnecessary imports to the biogas plant	0	0
Overfillings within the biogas plant	0	0
Total costs (€)	44,573,238.2	44,028,213.65

By comparing the performance of the optimized routings under the assumption of biomass time-criticality, as presented in Tables 3 and 4 in Chapter 4.2, with the performance of the randomized and the baseline routings under the same assumption of biomass time-criticality, as presented in Tables 7 and 8 above, similar conclusions can be drawn regarding the appropriateness of the developed simulation and optimization model. If the collection of biomasses is triggered solely by orders from farms occurring randomly, a high number of production stoppages may occur within a year, significantly contributing to the total costs of the system. Randomized routing introduces additional costs due to the extra kilometers driven during wrong visits.

5 DISCUSSION

This section analyzes and compares the results of the study presented in previous chapter. Finally, the chapter presents and discusses the key findings of the study.

5.1 Comparison of results

By comparing the results presented in Chapters 4.1 and 4.2, it is possible to develop perceptions of the impact on solutions, which may be influenced by the consideration of biomass time-criticality. Interestingly, the total distance driven by the vehicles and the number of visits to wrong types of sites by vehicles appear to be significantly lower when assuming biomass time-criticality. However, it remains unclear whether the difference between mileage and wrong visits is solely due to the assumption of biomass time-criticality.

The assumption of biomass time-criticality ultimately incorporates the continuous drying process of biomass within the sites, vehicles, and the biogas plant's storage into the simulation model, as presented in Equations 3 and 4, inspired by the biomass storage model by van Dyken et al. (2010). This process leads to a continuous decrease in the volume of biomass and an increase in its TS rate due to drying. Thus, it cannot be explicitly concluded that there is a cause-and-effect relationship between the drying process of biomasses and the mileage driven by vehicles transporting them based on these results. The possible improvement in mileage and wrong incorrect visits may also be attributed to pure coincidence, as there is a chance for the GA to become stuck in local optima if the optimization is terminated prematurely (Katoch et al. 2021). Consequently, further research on this topic is necessary.

It can be assumed that in a time-critical scenario, biogas yield should increase when the effects of time-criticality are minimized through efficient logistic routing. Therefore, if the increase in biogas yield exceeds the additional logistic costs incurred by driving extra kilometers, then it would be justifiable to do so. However, it's important to note that the model used in this study does not measure the actual amount of biogas produced within the plant; it only tracks the consumption of biomasses as resources. Consequently, conclusions about this observation cannot be drawn based on the study's results. The need for further research on the topic is justified once again.

However, based on these results, it can be stated that the passive processes occurring within the biomasses should be considered when planning the logistic routing of a circular system for transporting biomasses to biogas production. In both cases, the number

of production stoppages occurring within a year was managed to be reduced to zero with the optimized routing. Additionally, the consumption of dilution water and the total system costs appear to be lower when optimizing the routing under the assumption of biomass time-criticality. The actual availability of biomasses for use in biogas production may also be influenced by time-critical factors, as suggested by the lower number of overload days at the pickup sites when biomass time-criticality was considered. This can be explained by the assumption of biomass time-criticality. Storage levels at the pickup sites continuously decrease daily, resulting in fewer days when storage levels exceed their capacities.

Given the relatively high number of days with pickup site overloads in both cases, one might question whether nine vehicles are enough to collect biomasses from this many sites. On the other hand, the number of pickup sites was intentionally set to be this high to ensure an adequate supply of biomass for the annual resource consumption at the biogas plant. Therefore, using the number of pickup site overload days as a performance indicator and cost factor in this case may not be necessary. Based on this, its high value with the optimized routing can be partially ignored.

While part of the reduced cost is attributed to lower mileage and fewer wrong visits when considering biomass time-criticality, the key observation here is that the number of production stoppages remains at zero in both cases. This indicates a continuous biogas production process and biomass flow within the biogas plant. This highlights the potential cost savings through more efficient logistic planning, as it becomes evident that passive time-critical processes affecting the quality of biomasses for energy production do exist (van Dyken et al. 2010; Mönch-Tegeder et al. 2013; Hadin et al. 2016). The question, then, is whether decision-makers planning the logistic systems used within circular supply chains for the biogas production take these processes into consideration or not.

Additionally, after filtering out wrong visits from the optimized routings and rerunning the simulation with the filtered routings, the results appear to be promisingly good. It should be mentioned that wrong visits should be considered more as a feature of a solution that exists due to the deficiency of the GA. The GA utilized within the study's optimization generates routing proposals solely based on the locations that are given to it as an input. Therefore, it does not check or exclude the possible wrong visits arising within the generated routing, which is why the filtering procedure executed afterwards is appropriate. Wrong visits arising within the optimized routings indicates the suboptimality of the solution, since if the global optimum was found by the GA, wrong visits should not occur at all.

In real life, logistics operators know which type of sites they should visit, and therefore, wrong visits would not occur. This is also why filtering out wrong visits from the optimized solutions is justified. Continuous biogas production is ensured in both cases with no need for overtime work, and vehicles visit sites only of their type, reducing the kilometers and, therefore, total costs significantly. It remains unclear how far these results with the filtered routings are from the global optimum, as there is no reason to believe they are at the global optimum. On the other hand, it's not clear what cost factors the solutions could be improved upon. The need for further research on this topic is justified, as the development of methods for finding the global optimum solution is required.

The benchmarks of the results prove the benefits of planning the logistic routing of biomasses by utilizing dynamic optimization methods. As can be concluded from the benchmarks presented in Chapter 4.3, if the decision-making process for collecting biomasses is simply reactive to orders arising randomly from the farms, the continuous process of biogas production may be endangered, as observed with the high number of production stoppages within the benchmarks. In addition, excess kilometers are driven due to the reactive approach of collecting biomasses in an order-controlled manner, instead of planning the logistic routing while considering the resource needs and consumption within the biogas plant. Additionally, if the routing is completely random, a significant number of additional kilometers may be driven due to the wrong visits, decreasing the performance of the solution. On the other hand, the optimized routings are generated proactively by considering resource shortages, consumption of dilution water, total mileage driven by vehicles, and other relevant factors. The decision-making process for collecting the biomasses is more rational and sophisticated in comparison to reactive collection in an order-driven manner, which may significantly decrease the total costs of the system, ultimately making the circular supply chain more effective and enhancing the practices of the CBE.

5.2 Key findings

The objectives of the study included identifying critical general and case-specific factors for optimizing the logistic routing within a circular supply chain to ensure its compatibility with the CBE practices. This objective partially overlapped with the subobjectives of implementing spatial information mapping for biomasses located near the biogas plant, generating information about biomass availability, and subsequently identifying potential strategic partnerships for the case company. Using spatial information mapping of biomasses, the study aimed to plan and optimize logistic routing crucial to the biogas plant's production process. This optimization sought to achieve a continuous biogas production

and efficient biomass flow while simultaneously minimizing logistic costs by planning and optimizing routes for vehicles collecting and transporting biomasses from various sites to the biogas plant. Additionally, the study aimed to advance understanding of how passive time-critical processes occurring within the biomasses influence the optimization of logistic routing.

The objectives of the study were relatively well achieved. The factors needed to align logistic system operations with CBE practices were effectively addressed. This resulted in no significant deficiencies in the developed methodology, which models, simulates, and optimizes the functions of the components of the circular supply chain responsible for transporting biomass from farms to the biogas plant for biogas production. For example, the requirement that the TS-rate must be at most 15% within the biogas production process (Hadin & Eriksson, 2016) was probably the most important restriction related to CBE practices that was identified and considered in this study. Other identified and considered factors influencing the implementation of the CBE practices are presented in Figure 5 in Chapter 2.6.

The implementation of spatial information mapping for biomasses near the case company's biogas plant was successfully completed. As presented in Chapter 3.4, the phases during the data processing achieved the goal of mapping biomass potentials near the biogas plant. This process began with wide and unmapped datasets of biomasses located in Finland and concluded with mapping the biomass potentials within a 50 km radius of the biogas plant. It also proposed locations from which the biomasses should be picked up to meet the annual demand for biomasses within the biogas production process. Similar maps as presented in Chapter 3.4, can be found for all inspected biomasses of the study in GitHub (Eloranta, 2023c).

The study optimized and proposed a routing plan for the case company. By following this plan, logistic routing could be executed relatively cost-effectively, ensuring continuous biogas production at the biogas plant. The performance of the optimized routing plans was validated and assessed by comparing the values of selected performance indicators with randomized routings and routings corresponding to a practical approach to biomass routing. These performance indicators were the cost terms implemented within the simulation model, which were minimized during the routing optimization process. However, as demonstrated in Chapter 4, the optimized routings, which serves as the results of this study, may represent suboptimal solutions to the problem of BRBPP. Thus, the results likely provide sufficiently decent solutions for executing logistic operations, but they probably may be further optimized with additional computing time and power. Still, the results of the study successfully enable improving the efficiency of the case's circular supply

chain, as the optimized routing improve the factors presented in Figure 5 in Chapter 2.6 simultaneously considering the relevant factors of implementation of the CBE practices.

The final objective of the study was to examine how the consideration of time-critical factors, occurring as passive drying processes within the biomasses collected, transported, and used in biogas production, affects the solution of optimized routing. Based on the study's results, it may be concluded that considering passive processes that affect biomass quality in terms of their bioenergy potential could potentially lead to cost savings through more efficient logistic routing planning. However, since the study's results cannot be considered as the global optimum, a direct causal link between considering time-critical factors and reduced total system costs cannot be definitively established. Therefore, further research on this topic is required to authenticate the global optimality of the optimized routing.

6 CONCLUSIONS

This chapter concludes the study by discussing its theoretical and practical implications, addressing the study's limitations, assessing its quality, and presenting ideas for future research.

6.1 Theoretical and practical implications

The study has both theoretical and practical implications. Theoretical implications of the study include the initial definition of the biomass routing and biogas production problem (BRBPP) and the use of sophisticated optimization methodology in seeking a solution for the BRBPP. Since the study's results were determined to likely be suboptimal, the need for further research on the topic also serves as a theoretical implication of the study. It is possible that the developed methodology of the study may not be sufficient to fully optimize the BRBPP, given the complexity of the problem and the various factors influencing the solution's optimality. Additionally, the comparison of optimized results with and without the assumption of passive drying processes within the biomasses has theoretical implications. As examined in the study's results, considering passive drying processes within the biomasses may impact the optimization of logistic routing. Therefore, the BRBPP should be re-evaluated and considered from the perspective of time-criticality to ensure that the problem is appropriately addressed.

The primary practical contribution of the study is the development of tools and methodologies that can be used for geospatial mapping of large datasets (Eloranta, 2023a), as well as modeling and optimizing the logistic routing of biomass collection and transportation operations for use in centralized biogas plants (Niemitalo & Ekkerman, 2022; Eloranta, 2023b). The later utilization of these developed tools for biomass data processing, simulation, and optimization is not limited to the case company's biogas plant in the study. Instead, they enable the mapping of any geospatial biomass datasets and the modeling and optimization of logistics for collecting biomasses from farms, which can serve as feedstock for centralized biogas plants. The practical implications for the case company from the study include an optimized daily routing plan for collecting biomasses destined for the biogas plant. Furthermore, the geospatial mapping of biomasses conducted in this study allows the case company to gain a better understanding of the availability of various types of biomasses near the biogas plant, providing initial information on where and how far biomass collection can be efficiently carried out.

6.2 Quality assessment and limitations of the study

The study has certain limitations. One significant limitation pertains to the initial biomass data used in this study (LuKe, 2023), from which the cluster central points were calculated and modeled as pickup sites. The limitation lies in the usability of the study's results. The locations of these pickup sites were defined as the weighted central points of the clusters, even though their locations could have been determined using methods explicitly designed to define biomass collection points, such as the Borvemar model (Velázquez-Martí & Annevelink, 2009; Gracia et al. 2014). Since the pickup sites were generated by clustering the initial biomass datasets, the pickup sites modeled as farms within the simulation are, by their nature, theoretical and may not correspond to actual farms near the case company's biogas plant. This limitation must be acknowledged, as the biogas plant is still in the planning and design phase, and the actual farm-specific supplier network has not yet been established. However, once the actual farms are identified and confirmed as suppliers to the biogas plant, the developed simulation and optimization methodology of the study can be reused to produce more practical solutions for the execution of routing.

A potential limitation of the study is the lack of restrictions on the actual mix of biomasses used in biogas production. Currently, the developed model allows the composition of biomasses to change daily, from which biogas is assumed to be produced. However, this may not be realistically feasible, as there are optimization methods available for selecting the optimal composition of biomasses for anaerobic digestion to maximize methane production (Álvarez et al. 2010). These methods indicate the stable nature of the process and minimal changes in its composition.

Additional limitations are associated with the optimization of logistic routing, the use of the GA as the optimization method, and the high computing power it requires. As previously noted, optimization performed by the GA carries the risk of converging to a local optimum (Katoch et al. 2021). As concluded, the study's results are likely suboptimal, which could be a consequence of the GA becoming trapped in a local optimum. The suboptimality of the solution is emphasized by the apparent negative slope of the total cost curve at the end of the optimization process. The high number of wrong visits within the optimized routings suggests suboptimal results. However, it's important to note that wrong visits can be attributed to deficiencies within the GA used for optimization. After filtering out wrong visits from the optimized routings, the results appear promising but should still be considered suboptimal rather than the global optimum.

However, due to the high computational power required and the limited time available for the study, the number of generations was capped at 600,000 as a stopping criterion for optimization. If the optimization had been allowed to continue beyond 600,000 generations, it is possible that more optimal solutions could have been found. Nevertheless, due to the complexity of the problem, the choice of 600,000 generations was made to accommodate the constraints of available research time. Optimizing for 600,000 generations alone took roughly a week to compute with the hardware used in the study.

To account for limitations in computing power and time, the amount of noise was intentionally reduced in the study. Initially, there were plans to model the accumulation of biomasses at sites with noise terms, but these were omitted due to the aforementioned constraints. However, it remains unclear whether the inclusion of noise would have significantly improved the simulation model or merely added unnecessary complexity to the optimization process.

However, the validity of the developed methodology and the results it provides are supported by the benchmarks used when assuming an order-controlled approach to biomass collection. If the decision-making process for the heuristics governing the collection and transportation of biomass from farms to the plant relies solely on farm-generated orders, it can disrupt the continuous flow of resources and biogas production. In the real world, it is reasonable to assume that, to some extent, logistics operators employ order-controlled practices in biomass collection and transportation. However, this approach neglects other relevant factors within the biogas supply chain operations, leading to significant inefficiencies and additional costs, such as resource shortages and the need for dilution water to bring the biomass mix within the reactor to acceptable levels.

6.3 Ideas for future research

As the need for future research has been discussed in previous chapters, future studies on this topic could further advance optimization methods for solving the BRBPP. One promising avenue for development is the creation and implementation of optimization methodologies based on reinforcement learning (RL). Methods aimed at optimizing logistic systems based on RL have already been developed (Sun et al. 2019; Chen et al. 2022). Reinforcement learning is a sophisticated machine learning approach that has the potential to efficiently address the BRBPP. Unlike the GA, which seeks to improve the current best solution, RL also aims to learn the functioning of the system underlying the optimization problem (Sun et al. 2019; Chen et al. 2022). Incorporating RL into the opti-

mization of logistic routing within the context of BRBPP could provide a more comprehensive understanding of how passive time-critical processes within biomasses impact the performance of the optimized solution.

The model could be expanded to cover more of the biogas supply chain. This includes transporting excess digestate back to farms after the AD process. It also involves considering operations for supplying the actual biogas produced to clients.

Furthermore, in future research, the level of noise within the simulation model could be increased to create a more realistic model. For example, the accumulation process of manures could be modified to include a noise term, introducing randomness to the deterministic nature of manure accumulation. Similar noise terms could be introduced to various parts of the simulation model, such as the duration of collection operations performed by vehicles or the daily consumption of biomasses by the biogas plant from its storage. While increased noise would enhance the realism of the simulation model, it would also significantly complicate the optimization problem. Therefore, the inclusion of noise terms and their implications should be carefully considered before implementation in the simulation model.

REFERENCES

- Alcott, B. 2005, "Jevons' paradox", *Ecological Economics*, vol. 54, pp. 9–21.
- Álvarez, J., Otero, L. & Lema J. 2010, "A methodology for optimizing feed composition for anaerobic co-digestion of agro-industrial wastes", *Bioresource Technology*, vol. 101, pp. 1153–1158.
- Balaman, S. Y., Wright, D. G., Scott, J, Matopoulos, A. 2018, "Network design and technology management for waste to energy production: An integrated optimization framework under the principles of circular economy", *Energy*, vol. 143, pp. 911–933.
- Banasik, A., Kanellopoulos, A., Claassen, G., Bloemhof-Ruwaard, J. & van der Vorst, J. 2017, "Closing loops in agricultural supply chains using multi-objective optimization: A case study of an industrial mushroom supply chain", *International Journal of Production Economics*, vol. 183, pp. 409–420.
- Baños, R., Ortega, J., Gil, C., Márquez, A. & de Toro F. 2013, "A hybrid meta-heuristic for multi-objective vehicle routing problems with time windows", *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, vol. 65, pp. 286–296.
- Bauer, P., Stevens, B. & Hazeleger, W. 2021, "A digital twin of Earth for the green transition", *Nature Climate Change*, vol. 11 (2), pp. 80–83.
- Bellezoni, R. A., Adeogun, A. P., Paes, M. X. & Puppim de Oliveira, J. A. 2022, "Tackling climate change through circular economy in cities", *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 381135126.
- Berger, J. & Barkaoui, M. 2003, "A Hybrid Genetic Algorithm for the Capacitated Vehicle Routing Problem", *Genetic And Evolutionary Computation*, 2003, pp. 646–656.
- Bochtis, D. & Sørensen, C. 2009, "The vehicle routing problem in field logistics: Part I", *Biosystems Engineering*, vol. 104, pp. 447–457.
- Bochtis, D. & Sørensen, C. 2010, "The vehicle routing problem in field logistics: Part II", *Biosystems Engineering*, vol. 105, pp. 180-188.
- Bossle, M., de Barcellos, M., Vieira, L. & Sauvée L. 2016, "The drivers for adoption of eco-innovation", *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 113, pp. 861–872.
- Butemann, H. & Schimmelpfeng, K. 2020, "Long-term electricity production planning of a flexible biogas plant considering wear and tear", *Journal of Business Economics*, vol. 90, pp. 1289–1313.

Case company, 2023, "Maatalouden biomassojen hyödyntäminen uudella teknologialla!". The presentation material for the design and layout of the biogas plant.

Chaharsooghi, S. K. & Heydari, J. 2010, "Supply chain coordination for the joint determination of order quantity and reorder point using credit option", *European Journal of Operational Research*, vol. 204, pp. 86–95.

Chen, L., Hu, B., Guan, Z., Zhao, L. & Shen, X. 2022, "Multiagent Meta-Reinforcement Learning for Adaptive Multipath Routing Optimization", *IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks and Learning Systems*, vol. 33 no. 10. pp. 5374–5386.

Das, S. & Bhattacharyya, B. 2015, "Optimization of municipal solid waste collection and transportation routes", *Waste management*, vol. 43, pp. 9–18.

Demeter, K. & Matyusz, Z. 2011, "The impact of lean practices on inventory turnover", *International Journal of Production Economics*, vol. 133, pp. 154–163.

Donner, M., Gohier, R. & de Vries, H. 2020, "A new circular business model typology for creating value from agro-waste", *Science of the Total Environment*, 716137065.

Donner, M., Verniquet, A., Broeze, J., Kayser, K., De Vries, H. 2021, "Critical success and risk factors for circular business models valorising agricultural waste and by-products", *Resources, Conservation & Recycling*, 165105236.

Eloranta, K. 2023a, "data_processing.ipynb", Source code of the data procession tool, located in Github repository Dippa/Biomassa-atlas_data/data_processing.ipynb. Available at: https://github.com/Kaspereloranta/Dippa/blob/main/Biomassa-atlas_data/data_processing.ipynb. (Accessed 9.6.2023)

Eloranta, K. 2023b, "logistics_sim", Source code of case-specific, further developed version of the Logistics simulation and optimization (Niemitalo & Ekkerman, 2022). Available at: https://github.com/Kaspereloranta/Dippa/tree/main/logistics_sim. (Accessed at: 25.7.2023)

Eloranta, K. 2023c, "Biomassa-atlas_data", Geospatial data mapping of biomasses. Available at: https://github.com/Kaspereloranta/Dippa/tree/main/Biomassa-atlas_data. (Accessed at: 13.9.2023)

Geissdoerfer, M., Savaget, P., Bocken, N. & Hultink, E. 2017, "The Circular Economy – A new sustainability paradigm?", *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 143, pp. 757–768.

Geng, Y., Fu, J., Sarkis, J. & Xue, B. 2012, "Towards a national circular economy indicator system in China: an evaluation and critical analysis", *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 23 (1), p. 216–224.

Giampietro, M. 2019, "On the Circular Bioeconomy and Decoupling: Implications for Sustainable Growth", *Ecological Economics*, vol. 162, pp. 143–156.

Government Decree on the Restriction of Discharge of Nitrates From Agriculture into Waters 2000/931. Issued in Helsinki 9.11.2000. Available at: <https://www.finlex.fi/en/laki/kaanokset/2000/en20000931?search%5Btype%5D=pika&search%5Bkieli%5D%5B0%5D=en&search%5Bpika%5D=931%2F2000>. (Accessed at: 25.7.2023)

Gracia, C., Velázquez-Martí, B. & Estornell, J. 2014, "An application of the vehicle routing problem to biomass transportation", *Biosystems Engineering*, vol. 124, pp. 40–52.

Grafström, J. & Aasma, S. 2021, "Breaking circular economy barriers", *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 292126002.

Hadin, Å. & Eriksson, O. 2016, "Horse manure as feedstock for anaerobic digestion", *Waste Management*, vol. 56, pp. 506–518.

Hadin, Å., Eriksson, O. & Hillman, K. 2016, "A review of potential critical factors in horse keeping for anaerobic digestion of horse manure" *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 65, pp. 432–442.

Hojnik, J. & Ruzzier, M. 2016, "What drives eco-innovation? A review of an emerging literature", *Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions*, vol. 19, pp. 31–41.

Huang, Y., Fan, Y. & Chen C. 2014, "An Integrated Biofuel Supply Chain to Cope With Feedstock Seasonality and Uncertainty", *Transportation Science*, vol. 48, No. 4, November 2014, pp. 540–554.

Jeffares, A. 2019, "K-means: A Complete Introduction", *Towards Data Science*. Available at: <https://towardsdatascience.com/k-means-a-complete-introduction-1702af9cd8c>. (Accessed at: 9.6.2023)

Jensen, I., Münster, M. & Pisinger, D. 2017, "Optimizing the supply chain of biomass and biogas for a single plant considering mass and energy losses", *European Journal of Operational Research*, vol. 262, pp. 744–758.

Jozefowicz, N., Semet, F. & Talbi E. 2008, "Multi-objective vehicle routing problems", *European Journal of Operational Research*, vol. 189, pp. 293–309.

Jumppanen, A. 2023, "Vaihtoehto viljalle: Golden Fields Factory tavoittelee 20 000 hehtaarin nurmialaa", *AGRImedia*. Available at: <https://www.agrimedia.fi/golden-fields-factory-tavoittelee-20-000-hehtaarin-nurmialaa/>. (Accessed 23.5.2023)

- Kamilaris, A. & Prenafeta-Boldú, F. X. 2021, "Examining the perspectives of using manure from livestock farms as fertilizer to crop fields based on a realistic simulation", *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture*, 191106486.
- Karmakar, S., Kumar De, S. & Goswami A. 2017, "A pollution sensitive dense fuzzy economic production quantity model with cycle time dependent production rate", *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 154, pp. 139–150.
- Katoch, S., Chauhan, S. & Kumar, V. 2021 "A review on genetic algorithm: past, present, and future", *Multimedia Tools and Applications*, vol. 80, pp. 8091–8126.
- Kinyua, M., Wald, I., Camacho-Céspedes, F., Izurieta, R., Haas, C. & Ergas, S. 2016, "Does the use of tubular digesters to treat livestock waste lower the risk of infection from *Cryptosporidium parvum* and *Giardia lamblia*?", *Journal of Water and Health*, vol. 14 (5), pp. 738–753.
- Kirchherr, J., Piscicelli, L., Bour, R., Kostense-Smit, E., Muller, J., Huibrechtse-Truijens, A. & Hekkert, M. 2018, "Barriers to the Circular Economy: Evidence From the European Union (EU)", *Ecological Economics*, vol. 150, pp. 264–272.
- Korhonen, J., Honkasalo, A. & Seppälä, J. 2018, "Circular Economy: The Concept and its Limitations", *Ecological Economics*, vol. 143, pp. 37–46.
- Kymäläinen, M. & Tampio, E. 2023, "BioKanta – Biokaasua hiiliviisaasti ja ravinteet kiertoon Kanta-Hämeessä". Häme University of Applied Sciences (HAMK). Available at: <https://www.hamk.fi/biokanta>. (Accessed 5.4.2023)
- Lessman, M., Kanellopoulos, J., Kros, J., Orsi, F. & Bakker, M. 2023, "Maximizing agricultural reuse of recycled nutrients: A spatially explicit assessment of environmental consequences and costs", *Journal of Environmental Management*, 332117378.
- Liu, S., Zhang, Y., Liu, Y., Wang, L., Wang, X. 2019, "An 'Internet of Things' enabled dynamic optimization method for smart vehicles and logistics tasks", *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 215, pp. 806–820.
- Liu, Y., Gilchrist, A., Zhang, J. & Li, X. 2008, "Detection of Viable but Nonculturable *Escherichia coli* O157:H7 Bacteria in Drinking Water and River Water", *Applied and Environmental Microbiology*, vol. 74 (5), pp. 1502–1507.
- LuKe, 2023, Biomassa-atlas. Available at: <https://biomassa-atlas.luke.fi/>. (Accessed 9.6.2023)

- Luostarinen, S., Grönroos, J., Hellstedt, M., Nousiainen, J. & Munther, J. 2017, "Finnish Normative Manure System: System documentation and first results", *Natural resources and bioeconomy studies*, vol. 48/2017. Natural Resources Institute Finland. Helsinki.
- Magiya, J. 2019. "Clustering GPS Coordinates and Forming Regions with Python", *Level Up Coding by gitconnected.com*. Available at: <https://levelup.gitconnected.com/clustering-gps-co-ordinates-forming-regions-4f50caa7e4a1>. (Accessed at: 9.6.2023)
- Manyi-Loh, C., Mamphweli, S., Meyer, E., Okoh, A., Makaka, G. & Simon, M. 2013, "Microbial Anaerobic Digestion (Bio-Digesters) as an Approach to the Decontamination of Animal Wastes in Pollution Control and the Generation of Renewable Energy", *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, vol. 10, pp. 4390–4417.
- Mohan, S., Chiranjeevi, P., Dahiya, S. & Kumar, A. 2018, "Waste derived bioeconomy in India: A perspective", *New Biotechnology*, vol. 40, pp. 60–69.
- Monlau, F., Sambusiti, C., Ficara, E., Aboulkas, A., Barakat, A. & Carrère. 2015, "New opportunities for agricultural digestate valorization: current situation and perspectives", *Energy & Environmental Science*, vol. 8, pp. 2600–2621.
- Monteiro, E. & Ferreira, S. 2022, "Biomass Waste for Energy Production", *Energies*, vol. 15 (16), pp. 5943.
- Mönch-Tegeder, M., Lemmer, A., Oechsner, H. & Jungbluth, T. 2013, "Investigation of the methane potential of horse manure", *Agricultural Engineering International*, vol. 15, n. 2, pp. 161–172.
- Nag, R., Auer, A., Markey, B., Whyte, P., Nolan, S., O'Flaherty, V., Russell, L., Bolon, D., Fenton, O., Richards, K. & Cummins, E. 2019, "Anaerobic digestion of agricultural manure and biomass – Critical indicators of risk and knowledge gaps", *Science of the Total Environment*, vol. 690, pp. 460–479.
- Niemitalo, O. & Ekkerman, G. 2022, "Logistics simulation and optimization". Source code and the documentation of the original simulation and optimization models. Available at: https://github.com/hamk-uas/logistics_sim. (Accessed at: 20.7.2023)
- openrouteservice, 2023, "Routing API". Available at: <https://openrouteservice.org/>. (Accessed at: 20.7.2023)
- Paredes-Sánchez, J., López-Ochoa, L., López-González, L., Las-Heras-Casas, J. & Xiberta-Bernat, J. 2019, "Evolution and perspectives of the bioenergy applications in Spain", *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 213, pp. 553–568.

- Ponjavic, M., Karabegovic, A., Celebicanin, S. & Ljusa, M. 2020, "Performance indicators for poultry manure supply model analysis", *UPB Scientific Bulletin, Series D: Mechanical Engineering*, vol. 82, iss. 4.
- Prieto-Sandoval, V., Jaca, C. & Ormazabal, M. 2018, "Towards a consensus on the circular economy", *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 179, pp. 605–615.
- Ranta, V., Aarikka-Stenroos, L. & Väisänen, J-M. 2021, "Digital technologies catalyzing business model innovation for circular economy – Multiple case study", *Resources, Conservation & Recycling*, 164105155.
- Saji, B. 2023, "Elbow Method for Finding the Optimal Number of Clusters in K-Means" *Analytics Vidhya*. Available at: <https://www.analyticsvidhya.com/blog/2021/01/in-depth-intuition-of-k-means-clustering-algorithm-in-machine-learning/>. (Accessed: 15.6.2023)
- Sakar, S., Yetilmezsoy, K. & Kocak, E. 2009, "Anaerobic digestion technology in poultry and livestock waste treatment – a literature review", *Waste Management & Research*, vol. 27 (1), pp. 3–18.
- Salvador, R., Puglieri, F., Halog, A., de Andrade, F., Piekarski, C. & Francisco, A. 2021, "Key aspects for designing business models for a circular bioeconomy", *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 278, 124341.
- Saunders, M., Lewis, P. & Thornhill, A. 2019, "Research methods for business students". 8th edition. Harlow: Pearson.
- Schütz, F. 2021, "SimCpp20 – a discrete-event simulation framework for C++". Available at: <https://github.com/fschuetz04/simcpp20>. (Accessed: 20.7.2023)
- scikit-learn developers, 2023, sklearn.cluster.KMeans, *scikit-learn*. Available at: <https://scikit-learn.org/stable/modules/generated/sklearn.cluster.KMeans.html>. (Accessed at: 9.6.2023)
- Sevgen, A. & Sargut, F. Z. 2019, "May reorder point help under disruptions?", *International Journal of Production Economics*, vol. 209, pp. 61–69.
- Shabani, N. & Sowlati, T. 2013, "A mixed integer non-linear programming model for tactical value chain optimization of a wood biomass power plant", *Applied Energy*, vol. 104, pp. 353–361.
- Stahel, W. R. 2016, "The circular economy", *Nature*, vol. 531 (7595), pp. 435–438.
- Stevenson, W. J. 2014, "Operations management", 12th ed., global ed. New York, NY: McGraw Hill/Irwin.

- Su, G., Ong, H., Zulkifili, N., Ibrahim, S., Chen, W., Chong, C. & Ok, Y. 2022, "Valorization of animal manure via pyrolysis for bioenergy: A review", *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 343, 130965.
- Sun, P., Hu, Y., Lan, J., Tian, L. & Chen, M. 2019, "TIDE: Time-relevant deep reinforcement learning for routing optimization", *Future Generation Computer Systems*, vol. 99, pp. 401–409.
- Tampio, E. 2023, "Biokaasua hiiliviisaasti ja ravinteet kiertoon Kanta-Hämeessä – BioKanta – TP1.3 Humppilan casen aloituskokous 23.3.2023". The presentation material for the BioKanta project meeting.
- Team SimPy, 2020, "Discrete event simulation for Python". Available at: <https://simpy.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>. (Accessed: 20.7.2023)
- van Dyken, S., Bakken, B. & Skjelbred, H. 2010, "Linear mixed-integer models for biomass supply chains with transport, storage and processing", *Energy*, vol. 35, pp. 1338–1350-
- Varenova, D., Samy, M. & Combs, A. 2013, "Corporate social responsibility and profitability: trade-off or synergy - Perceptions of executives of FTSE All-Share companies", *Sustainability Accounting, Management and Policy Journal*, vol. 4 (2), pp. 190–215.
- Velázquez-Martí B. & Annevelink, E. 2009, "GIS application to define biomass collection points as sources for linear programming of delivery networks", *Transactions of ASABE*, vol. 52 (4), pp. 1069–1078.
- Yu, B., Liu, X., Ji, C. & Sun H. 2023, "Greenhouse gas mitigation strategies and decision support for the utilization of agricultural waste systems: A case study of Jiangxi Province, China", *Energy*, vol. 265, 126380.
- Yuan, Z., Bi, J. & Moriguchi, Y. 2006, "The Circular Economy: A New Development Strategy in China", *Journal of Industrial Ecology*, vol. 10 (1-2), pp. 4–8.
- Wang, Z., Bui, Q., Zhang, B. & Pham, T. 2020, "Biomass energy production and its impact on the ecological footprint: An investigation of G7 countries", *Science of the Total Environment*, 140741.
- Wei, X., Liu, Q., Pu, A., Wang, S., Chen, F., Zhang L., Zhang, Y., Dong, Z. & Wan X. 2022, "Knowledge Mapping of bioeconomy: A bibliometric analysis", *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 373133824.

Zhang, J., Osmani, A., Awudu, I. & Gonela, V. 2013, "An integrated optimization model for switchgrass-based bioethanol supply chain", *Applied Energy*, vol. 102, pp. 1205–1217.